

BIO-SUSHY

Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings

D1.3 Value chain analysis for NEW COATINGS

Deliverable Information	
Responsible partner:	ZSI
Work package No and Title:	WP1 BIO-SUSHY Specifications, Alignment & Social Acceptance
Contributing partner(s):	All partners
Dissemination level:	PU - Public
Type:	R - Document, report
Due date:	31/01/2025
Submission date:	31/01/2025
Version:	Final Version (V3)

Project Profile

Program	Horizon Europe
Call	HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01-23: Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials (RIA)
Number	101091464
Acronym	BIO-SUSHY
Name	Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings
Start Date	1 January 2023
Duration	48 months
Type of action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Granting authority	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
Project Coordinator	MATERIA NOVA

Document History

Version	Date	Entity	Remarks
V1	13/01/2025	ZSI, AXIA	First draft, including AXIA's survey input
V2	23/01/2025	ZSI, WoodK+, IFTH, RESCOLL, MANO	Updates from project partners. Specific comments on value chains by WoodK+, IFTH, RESCOLL, MANO
V3	31/01/2025	ZSI	Final Version

Publishable Summary

This document presents Deliverable 1.3 of the BIO-SUSHY project and is meant to aid the project's strategy to strengthen its value chains, building on safe and sustainable-by-design (SSbD) principles. Crucial in this endeavour are the project's efforts to integrate life cycle and safety aspects into the development phase and across its value chains. To help fulfill that aim, this report aims to identify and understand the relevant needs, demands, reservations and perceptions with regards to PFAS-free coatings in textile, food trays and cosmetic glass containers. The analysis identifies key trends in the uptake of new coatings in general, while subsequently zooming in on each of the three different value chains. Analysis is based on extensive desk research into the relevant issues, on the insights from 30 interviews with domain experts and stakeholders, on transdisciplinary exchange within the project, and on exploratory stakeholder surveys.

Since PFAS-replacement plays a central role in the project's objectives and is likely to significantly shape the future viability of its solutions, explicit attention is paid to the framework conditions this issue presents. Discussed are: pollution & health issues as a major motivation behind the need for PFAS replacement; social awareness and public trust as a driver of consumer preferences; relevant regulatory developments as potential catalysers of BIO-SUSHY solutions; trends in the chemicals, coatings, and new materials sectors; and innovation policies for industry growth & sustainability.

What follows is the identification and analysis of relevant considerations for the further establishment of the three BIO-SUSHY PFAS-free supply chains: paper food tray coatings, textile coatings, and cosmetic glass packaging coatings. This is done by analysing a wide range of value chain considerations and concerns in the three value chains and developing these insights into a comprehensive overview of the priorities for each of the value chains. Keeping in mind the early stage technology readiness level of the solutions (currently around TRL 4 at T0+25 months), there is an emphasis on factors that can aid the process of strengthening the future value chains based on SSbD principles.

After that stakeholder perceptions and feedback are examined, identifying collaboration opportunities and aligning BIO-SUSHY's solutions with market and technical priorities. What follows are key insights into strategic priorities, highlighting BIO-SUSHY's role in advancing safer, sustainable value chains and supporting circular and bioeconomy transitions. The deliverable ends with strategic priorities and next steps for improving the co-design process of BIO-SUSHY solutions and the mitigation of barriers to social acceptance.

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
Cefic	European Chemical Industry Council
CLP	Classification, Labelling, and Packaging Regulation
CSS	Chemical Strategy for Sustainability
DPP	Digital Product Pass
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EEA	European Environmental Agency
EPR	Extended producer responsibility
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance
FSC	Forest Stewardship Council
IIHC	Investor Initiative on Hazardous Chemicals
IRC	Initiative for Responsible Carnauba
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
PBS	Polybutylene succinate
PDMS	Polydimethylsiloxane
PEFC	Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
PFOA	Perfluorooctanoic acid
PFOS	Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid
PHBV	Polyhydroxyalkanoate
POP	Persistent Organic Pollutant
QSAR	Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship
RSPO	Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil
S-LCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
TEOS	Tetraethyl orthosilicate
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VOCs	Volatile Organic Compounds
ZDHC	Zero Discharge of Hazardous Chemicals

1. Introduction

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) are a group of chemicals widely used for their water and oil repellency properties in various applications, including non-stick cookware surfaces, textile treatments, and coatings for cardboard food packaging. Because of their widespread applicability and effectiveness, the discovery of PFAS has long been praised as "a miracle of science" (Renfrew & Pearson, 2021). However, in recent years, knowledge and awareness with regards to the negative impacts of PFAS has been on the rise and they have now become dubbed as "forever chemicals"; a term that emphasises the fact that they are long lasting chemicals, components of which break down extremely slowly (Hendlin, 2021). The insights into their negative impacts have sparked an outcry for restrictive regulatory action, which is increasingly being put into place by governments. A pivotal example here is the PFAS restriction proposal, published by the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) in 2023. Furthermore, public attention for PFAS' impact on human health and the environment is also rising.

Crucially, these kinds of developments are driving a push towards the development of PFAS alternatives in different domains. Considerable promise can be found in bio-based and hybrid materials that have the potential to provide similar functionalities without the associated health and environmental risks. The BIO-SUSHY Horizon Europe research project is heavily invested in these developments, with its commitment to help advance the transition to sustainable alternatives. In short, BIO-SUSHY's first goal is to develop high-quality, durable, and sustainable composite coatings that are based on different processing technologies (bio-based thermoplastic powders and hybrid sol-gel technologies). These innovative coating solutions should function as alternatives to PFAS coatings in three different areas of application: disposable paper food packaging, textiles, and cosmetic glass packaging.

Second, another important goal of the project is defined by BIO-SUSHY's emphasis on these alternatives' safety and sustainability: the coating solutions are explicitly being developed under the Safe- and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) framework. BIO-SUSHY aims at the further development and implementation of this framework by providing innovative contributions. As a result, an important outcome of the project will be its SSbD strategy of which the criteria are focused on the assessment of materials' risk toxicity and hazardous leachate as well as the life cycle assessment (LCA) of economic and environmental impacts.

By working on this combination of aims, the project supports the sustainable application of its high-quality, durable, and sustainable organic and hybrid coatings while directly aligning with the ambition of the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) toward a "toxic-free environment" (European Commission, 2020). In that context, this deliverable aims to analyse the early-stage value chains of the coatings that are being developed in BIO-SUSHY. It focuses on the unique challenges and opportunities within each value chain, as well as those of the project as a whole. In this way, the goal is to support the development of innovative, safe, and sustainable coatings that align with sustainability, regulatory, and market demands.

1.1. Study aim

This report on the BIO-SUSHY value chains aims to provide insights that can help to strengthen the project's efforts on establishing safe, sustainable, and resilient value chains for biobased and hybrid PFAS substitution in the coatings domain. Thus, the idea is to offer a transparent perspective on the key components and processes that are essential for establishing these value chains. By creating a more thorough understanding of the elements that contribute to this process, existing value chains can be transformed quicker, while potential new value chains can become established in the expanding domain of PFAS-free coatings. Crucially, this is happening in a rather volatile environment: both regulatory developments and consumer preferences are generally in flux, while the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of the coatings is still in earlier to intermediate development stages.

In practice, the report aims to uncover the opportunities for accelerating SSbD-based practices in the three BIO-SUSHY value chains and point at potential areas of improvement, innovation, and collaboration. Important to note here is that this type of strategy development is a complex endeavour that this report is only starting to assess: at stages of more advanced development, with a higher TRL, it is possible to further strengthen the focus on upscaling for commercial readiness. At that stage (around TRL 7-9), assessments can be made in more detail. This will likely fall outside of the project's scope, since the goal is to achieve TRL 5-6 at the end of the project. Consequently, key recommendations of the report focus on providing more detailed understandings of the way in which the project can strategically adjust to framework conditions in its implementation of bio-based and hybrid coatings.

1.2. Study approach & scope

In terms of analytic approach, this report aims to help the implementation of SSbD in the project's value chains. A major ambition of SSbD as a concept is to increase both the regulatory preparedness and societal uptake of innovations by eliminating the use of hazardous and high-impact substances at early stages of research. Also important is the fact that the ambition of the SSbD concept is to promote a whole life-cycle approach and is thus also aiming to ensure safety and sustainability along the entire value chain (Joint Research Centre et al., 2022).

In order to ensure and promote such an approach for the analysis of value chains in a context of research and innovation, the analysis of this deliverable builds on a quadruple helix model of innovation. This model is meant to understand and manage innovation by putting an emphasis on the interactions and collaborations between government, industry, academia and civil society. As such, this framework is often seen to represent a shift from a linear and top-down approach to a more collaborative model, of which the explicit aim is to involve a wide range of stakeholders.

Figure 1: SSbD Dimensions reveal a holistic, whole life-cycle approach. Source: (ANALYST Project, 2024)

In general, the quadruple helix model (see a visualisation in figure 2) is useful to support the holistic ambitions of the SSbD concept since it aims to recognise complex patterns of societal, economic and technological interdependence. Within such a context, it is useful to refer to the notion of sociotechnical systems in which the interactions among all the different social and technical elements and dimensions determine the function of the innovation system at large. By recognising the role of this wide range of actors in the innovation process, a solid focus on the embeddedness of innovation in society can be ensured. This includes a range of socially relevant issues, such as the sustainability of an innovation, or the attention for its (potential) societal impacts. As such, this approach is also meant to increase the social acceptance and adoption of innovations in the long run. Additionally, the involvement of elements like civil society can generally help strengthen the project's opportunities by fostering trust in bio-based and hybrid alternatives.

Figure 2: Visualisation of the quadruple helix framework. Source: (Finkelievich, 2016, p. 64)

Finally, in the BIO-SUSHY project, there are several other tasks and associated deliverables that address closely related topics:

- Task 1.4 - Analysing the willingness-to-pay and co-designing a social acceptance strategy: Especially when it comes to co-designing a social acceptance strategy for BIO-SUSHY, the value chain considerations in this report, including its focus on the holistic interpretation of SSbD, are crucial to provide a basis for the work on social acceptance.
- Task 4.3 - LCA, circularity, EoL solutions: This task contains LCA and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA). Especially with regards to the S-LCA, we have worked extensively with our project partner Wood K Plus in order to exploit the synergies.
- Task 5.2 - Innovation and Business Plan Activities: This task contains a PESTLE Analysis as well as a SWOT Analysis. The former is particularly relevant for the socioeconomic background that is discussed in Section 2, whereas the latter has provided useful insights for the challenges and opportunities discussed in Section 4.

1.3. Methods

With regards to methodology, each value chain has its own specific characteristics, which can only be effectively understood and studied by gathering an understanding of the wider issues (Kaplinsky & Morris, 2000). A quantitative approach is often used to describe the situation in well-established value chains, especially if sufficient amounts of quantitative data are available. For BIO-SUSHY, it is important to consider the fact that its bio-based and hybrid coatings are still being developed. As a result, the report looks at the considerations that are important at this stage. In such cases, qualitative approaches (e.g. interview data) can be used to get a better understanding of value chain specificities, especially when it involves strategy development for products that are in earlier stages of development. Apart from that however, exploratory surveys can be used to enrich these findings. In that context, the following methods are used for this report:

Desk research

The aim of the desk research is to gather insights related to the socioeconomic impact of BIO-SUSHY coatings and develop an initial overview of the relevant stakeholders and their positions. More specifically this includes material like:

- Exploration of reports from other funded projects and other initiatives focused on PFAS substitution.
- News and statements following the proposed ECHA ban on PFAS that was published at the beginning of 2023. Even though this ban is not yet in effect, the discussions about it provide informative insights into a variety of stakeholders' visions on the matter.
- Position papers and statements published by different types of organisations on issues like the above-mentioned ECHA ban, but also on other topics related to BIO-SUSHY's themes, such as the future of a sustainable chemical industry, SSbD, bio-based materials and so on.
- Academic literature on closely related background topics like PFAS-related issues, toxicology, bio-based materials sustainability transitions, etc.

Inter- and transdisciplinary learning

Inter- and transdisciplinary learning is an essential method in contexts where addressing complex societal and technological challenges requires collaboration across disciplines. This approach entails active engagement with participants from other fields to learn about their methods, perspectives, and priorities, ultimately enriching one's own understanding and practices. In order to gain critical insights into the technical design processes, operational constraints, and practical challenges that shape the development of coatings, this knowledge enhances the analysis by grounding it in the realities of technical implementation, while also contributing to a shared understanding of the societal implications of the developed solutions.

Such learning is not merely an exchange of knowledge but also a reflexive process that fosters mutual understanding. Engagement with other fields enables the development of a shared language and framework that bridges disciplinary boundaries, enabling innovative solutions to emerge. Inter- and transdisciplinary learning, therefore, is both a method of inquiry and a transformative practice, reinforcing the importance of collaboration in producing robust and contextually informed outcomes in social acceptance research.

Interviews

For this report, 30 interviews were conducted between May 2023 and January 2025 to develop a clear overview of the issues around the BIO-SUSHY value chains, focusing on different areas of inquiry. The interviews covered a wide range of stakeholders from the different value chains, as well as in more general, cross-cutting domains (e.g. PFAS regulation). Examples of stakeholders are: individual companies, national associations, European stakeholder associations, academics on different project-related topics, civil society representatives. The sample was developed based on the desk research as well as on snowball sampling and interactions with/advice from other project members.

The implicit aim of the questions in these semi-structured interviews was to address the different major topics from all components of the quadruple helix, as they had been predominantly identified during the desk research. The focus here was not to strictly separate technical and societal issues, but much rather to already link them at the earliest stage possible. Thereby, the core character of the interview sessions could be described as a transdisciplinary effort, linking different perspectives. In practical terms, this meant for instance that interviewees with a more technical background were also asked questions about social topics and vice versa.

Surveys

To enrich the findings, AXIA developed and distributed surveys among stakeholders. The aim was to gather additional data on:

- Additional stakeholders' perceptions of the new coatings.
- Any reservations or concerns they may have.
- Feedback on the proposed solution from the BIO-SUSHY project.

The main objectives of these surveys were to assess that innovations were well-received to improve the project's dissemination and exploitation strategies.

The surveys were tailored to capture feedback on stakeholders' perceptions, needs, concerns, and potential barriers to adoption. The following surveys were distributed:

1. Stakeholder perception survey
2. Consumer acceptance survey
3. Regulatory and compliance stakeholder survey

The surveys aimed to gather insight into the perceptions and attitudes of various stakeholders toward the new coatings. Table 1 illustrates the main objectives and the related target audience of these surveys.

Objectives and target audiences

The surveys aimed to gather insight into the perceptions and attitudes of various stakeholders toward the new coatings. Table 1 illustrates the main objectives and the related target audience of these surveys.

Survey	Objective	Target audience
Stakeholder perception	To gather insight into the perceptions and attitudes of various stakeholders towards the new coatings	Industrial stakeholders such as coating formulators, food service companies, clothing and textile producers, and glass cosmetic manufacturers
Consumer acceptance	To understand consumer attitudes towards products that utilize the new coatings	General consumers (potential users of products with the new coatings)
Regulatory and compliance	To assess the perspectives of regulatory bodies and public market-shaping entities on the new coatings	Regulatory bodies, public entities (e.g., European Chemicals Agency, European Food Safety Authority)

Table 1: Corresponding objectives and target audiences for the developed surveys.

Survey distribution strategy

A multi-channel distribution strategy was implemented. In particular, the project partners' network and the existent and consolidated project's communication channels, such as website and social media, were employed.

Project Partners' Network

BIO-SUSHY project partners were asked to distribute the surveys within their networks via email. This strategy was set up to reach industry stakeholders, regulatory bodies, and NGOs with whom they regularly interact. Partners were encouraged to personalize the message, highlighting the importance of participation in shaping the outcomes of the BIO-SUSHY project in replacing PFAS-free coatings.

BIO-SUSHY Project's Communication Channels

Survey links were posted on the BIO-SUSHY LinkedIn page and X profile with a dedicated creation of visuals and a brief description of the survey's purpose and importance to the project. Partners, sister projects, and followers were invited to share the post within their networks to reach a broader audience. Relevant hashtags and tags were also used.

For an insight into the display of survey on the website and social media channels, see [Annex IV](#).

Survey design

The design of each questionnaire and the related questions were specifically tailored to the target audience identified for each questionnaire. The goal was to collect relevant and actionable information from the respondents while keeping it condensed to be under the 5-minute time required to fill them out.

AXIA designed the questionnaire with input from ZSI. Generally, each survey was divided into three central parts:

- Introduction: brief introduction of the BIO-SUSHY project, the survey's purpose, and the importance of respondent feedback. A brief mention on the confidentiality of responses (anonymous) and the privacy policy .
- Questions: The initial questions were set to segment the demographics of the respondents and then specific to the identified questionnaire.
- Conclusions: Participants were thanked for their participation and informed about how the project would be used. A link to the project website was provided to allow them to explore the project further and follow the social media channels to remain updated.

Survey outcomes are discussed in [Section 4](#). For survey responses see [Annex I, II, and III](#).

1.4. Structure

What follows are five more sections, each addressing critical aspects of the BIO-SUSHY project and its contribution to advancing PFAS-free, sustainable coatings.

Section 2 provides an overview of the broader framework conditions influencing the development of sustainable coatings. It explores environmental, social, regulatory, industrial, and policy settings, highlighting the interplay of factors that shape the need for alternatives to PFAS. These insights establish the context for the BIO-SUSHY project and its holistic approach to safe and sustainable value chains.

Section 3 delves into the specific value chains of BIO-SUSHY solutions, analysing pivotal factors such as feedstock availability, innovation opportunities, regulatory environments, and sustainability considerations. It offers a forward-looking perspective on how these value chains may evolve as the technology matures, with a focus on disposable paper food packaging coatings, textile coatings, and cosmetic glass packaging coatings.

Section 4 analyses perceptions, reservations, and feedback from surveys conducted with key value chain stakeholders. The findings highlight opportunities for collaboration and identify areas where BIO-SUSHY's solutions can align with stakeholder priorities, enhancing both technical viability and market relevance.

Section 5 synthesises the insights gained from previous sections into strategic priorities for the project. It identifies BIO-SUSHY's potential to drive safer and more sustainable value chains, explores novel solutions aligned with stakeholder and consumer needs, and discusses the project's alignment with circular and bioeconomy transformations. The section also outlines the importance of sustainable upscaling and collaboration within the project's framework.

Finally, Section 6 concludes the report by reflecting on the progress made and the path forward for BIO-SUSHY in contributing to PFAS-free, sustainable value chains.

2. Framework conditions for PFAS-free, sustainable coatings

PFAS have been manufactured since the 1950s, following their accidental discovery by DuPont chemists in 1938 during research on refrigerant gases (Gaines, 2023). With over 6,000 compounds in use, PFAS have long been appreciated for their nonstick, waterproof, and stain-resistant properties, making them essential to a wide range of products, from food packaging to firefighting foams. This extensive use underscores the multi-faceted character of the search for PFAS substitution, necessitating an intricate interplay of industry, regulation, innovation, and consumer demand.

In support of BIO-SUSHY's goal to establish safe and sustainable value chains, insights into the broader framework conditions can help to understand the need for sustainable coatings. These contextual factors provide essential background information, thus supporting the establishment of a clearer vision for the uptake of BIO-SUSHY solutions. Understanding this broader landscape is crucial for building strategic visions, especially as the project operates within a rather volatile and unpredictable environment. In this context, it can help build a strategic vision that capitalises on emerging opportunities for sustainable coatings and strengthen their value chains in the near future.

Apart from providing necessary context, it is also useful to gain insights into topics inherent to the wider context of SSbD, like responsible sourcing, general due diligence in project activities, sustainable procurement, production & consumption, and issues of responsibility in the value chain. Considering the fact that the SSbD concept promotes ethical, sustainable, and socially conscious practices, these topics shall be included as much as possible and as early as possible in the development of new coating solutions. As such, the study of value chains is deliberately connected with activities that are concerned with (re-)establishing public trust in a biobased chemical industry and social acceptance of biobased and hybrid coatings.

The section divides five different, interrelated settings that describe the framework conditions defining the current need for PFAS alternatives. The first setting considers topics regarding environmental and public health. Second, the social setting, including issues related to PFAS awareness and the need to (re-)build public trust. Third, the regulatory setting with a focus on the past and present regulatory developments (with a focus on the EU). Fourth, current trends in the chemical industry itself, with a focus on elements that are pushing for phasing out PFAS and the need for sustainable alternatives. Fifth and last, EU industrial policy and green policy developments, as a key enabler for sustainable growth.

2.1. Setting 1: Environmental pollution & public health

Summary:

- Research insights on PFAS' environmental & public health impacts have increased steadily
- Expert voices in a wide range of areas paint an increasingly clear, distressing picture with regard to PFAS impact
- PFAS is increasingly seen as a major component in the transgression of planetary boundaries, specifically when it comes to the boundary of "novel entities"
- PFAS exposure is caused by factors like: pollution hotspots at production sites, use in a wide range of products, and generally to its extreme persistence
- Societal costs of PFAS pollution are high, including health system expenses and

environmental costs

PFAS are now ubiquitous in the environment, threatening ecosystems worldwide. Also, exposure of humans to PFAS has become a major public health concern. Especially in domains like environmental science & toxicology, public health & epidemiology, and environmental chemistry, increasing insights have heightened scrutiny on PFAS production and use, creating an urgent momentum for sustainable alternatives like BIO-SUSHY's coatings.

PFAS and the environment

There is an increasing sense of urgency with regards to the PFAS as a form of environmental pollution. In summary, PFAS are toxic, bioaccumulative and persistent due to their resistance to microbial degradation. A key issue is that PFAS substances can easily detach from PFAS-containing products, for instance through wear, off-gassing, or contact with water. This happens at nearly every stage of their life cycle, from production to disposal. As a result, PFAS particles often move into the environment, even after they have been disposed of in landfills, where they leach into groundwater and/or surface water. Another problematic issue is the migration of PFAS particles: PFAS can be transported over long distances through atmospheric currents or travel in the form of contaminated water. This has contributed to their global distribution. It has been demonstrated that areas far from direct sources of PFAS pollution are still being affected (even in the Arctic and Antarctic) (Panieri et al., 2022).

As a result, PFAS have now become ubiquitous in the environment which threatens ecosystems worldwide. Recent studies indicate widespread exposure with levels varying based on proximity to human populations and dietary habits. In animals, this leads to weakened immunity, liver damage, developmental and reproductive problems, impacts on the nervous and endocrine systems, gastrointestinal diseases related to the gut microbiome, and more (Guynup, 2023). As such, PFAS presents an additional danger to already vulnerable species worldwide (Environmental Working Group, 2024).

In line with this status, PFAS are currently seen to be an important component of the current crisis of our planetary boundaries as quantified by researchers from the Stockholm Resilience Centre. In their most recent analysis they have for the first time quantified the boundary named "Novel Entities" (Richardson et al., 2023). It is exactly this boundary that is one of the most severely transgressed among all the planetary boundaries (see Figure 3). PFAS is seen as an important driver of this problem. Given the 50-fold increase in chemical production since 1950, with projections to triple again by 2050, there is an urgent need for innovative bio-based and circular solutions to mitigate this threat.

Figure 3: Planetary boundaries as assessed by the Stockholm Resilience Centre. Source: (Stockholm Resilience Centre, 2022)

Health concerns

Also human exposure to PFAS has become a major public health concern. Because PFAS binds to proteins in the blood, they are transported throughout the body. Studies have detected PFAS in a wide variety of consumer products. In addition, several large scale programmes for screening have provided insights with regards to the presence of PFAS. For instance, the European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU) did a large scale study on a range of toxic chemicals which included more than 13.000 people from 28 European countries. One of their findings was that PFAS is present in the blood of all young people they surveyed. Furthermore, in up to a quarter of the cases, these people were exposed to concentrations where negative health effects could no longer be ruled out with sufficient certainty (Apel et al., 2020; Ortiz & European Environmental Bureau, 2023).

With regards to the specifics of health impact, research has suggested a likely risk for neurotoxicity. The UN Special Rapporteur on toxics and human rights, has argued that PFAS is currently causing a “silent pandemic” of diseases, disabilities and premature death (UN Special Rapporteur on toxics and human rights, 2022). Moreover, research of the effects of PFAS in humans indicates there is evidence that PFAS exposure can be associated with attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) as well as with an increased risk of developing neurodegenerative disorders such as Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease (Sammi et al., 2019). Also, PFAS are linked to certain types of cancer as well as infertility (Fenton et al., 2021).

Costs to society and need for alternatives

In direct relation to pollution and health issues, the societal costs of PFAS pollution are considerable. Scholars specialising in environmental pollution and public health stress the urgency of restricting

PFAS emissions and use. For the health system alone, the annual costs in the countries part of the European Economic Area are estimated at €52–84 billion (Goldenman et al., 2019). Beyond health, environmental remediation presents an even greater challenge, with clear solutions often lacking. A 2023 report by the Swedish NGO ChemSec estimates the global costs of PFAS pollution to reach €16 trillion (ChemSec, 2023). Given these costs, it is unsurprising that the production and use of PFAS materials have become a significant source of concern. Meanwhile, production sites have come under heightened scrutiny, further complicating the issue for industries. In particular, growing public concern about the (daily) use of consumer products containing PFAS, such as coatings, adds to this pressure (see Section 2.2).

For the BIO-SUSHY value chain, the increasing attention to environmental and health impacts of PFAS represents mostly opportunities:

- The need for safer, more sustainable coatings creates a critical momentum for exploring alternatives. The coatings developed within BIO-SUSHY promise reduced environmental impact and improved human safety.
- As research progresses, these innovations demonstrate their potential to enable industries to transition to eco-friendly practices, aligning with regulatory pressures and increasing consumer demand for safer products.
- However, as will become clear later in the report, it is important to actively work on efforts towards safe and sustainable solution that avoid regrettable substitution

2.2. Setting 2: Public awareness & trust

Summary:

- PFAS pollution is increasingly becoming a mainstream issue in public discourse, especially in regions where pollution hotspots are exposed
- Another important discussion concerns the use of PFAS in consumer products and the ramifications in terms of both environmental and human exposure
- PFAS issues can (further) erode the public trust in the chemical industry, as well as in specific industries, like food packaging, textiles and cosmetics industries
- Consumer markets for PFAS-free and/or bio-based products can use this momentum

The PFAS issue has increasingly entered mainstream discussions, accompanied by growing awareness of its environmental impact and toxicity. This has heightened consumer consciousness regarding PFAS-based products and contributes to a broader erosion of trust in the chemical industry and its products. These dynamics place greater pressure on producers of PFAS chemicals and consumer products containing them while simultaneously creating opportunities for alternatives.

Public awareness

Many environmental and health concerns linked to PFAS are now reflected in the social discourse (Kemper et al., 2024). Public awareness on the issue has expanded significantly, with a broad range of stakeholder groups raising concerns about the social and environmental risks of PFAS. Initiatives like the *Forever Pollution Project* (see Figure 4), a collaboration involving major media outlets such as the French *Le Monde* and the German *Süddeutsche Zeitung*, aim to reveal the extent of PFAS pollution

(Le Monde, 2023; Süddeutsche Zeitung, 2023). Furthermore, widely watched documentaries such as *The Devil We Know* as well as films like *Dark Waters* have further amplified public dialogue and advocacy on PFAS (Haynes, 2019; Soechtig & Seifert, 2019). These developments have not only affected the negative image of PFAS producers, but are also likely impacting the perception of numerous consumer products containing these substances.

Figure 4: Map (screenshot) of known and presumptive contamination sites across Europe from the Forever Pollution Project. Source: (Forever Pollution Project, 2023)

Furthermore, when looking at national contexts, the rise of high-profile cases drawing attention to pollution hotspots has had substantial implications for the social context. Examples of such cases are contamination near military bases or industrial production sites, as well as communities served by contaminated water supplies. This has raised awareness among residents and the wider public about the presence of PFAS in the environment and its potential health effects. Furthermore, exposure of

pollution hotspots has sparked activism within affected communities with grassroots movements demanding action from government agencies and industry to address the pollution and protect public health (Lorenzi, 2024; Menegatto & Zamperini, 2023). These pollution hotspots are already leading to legal actions, including lawsuits against companies responsible for PFAS contamination and litigation seeking compensation for affected communities (Wallender & Bloomberg, 2022). Current legal settlements and court rulings are expected to set precedents for future cases.

Consumer consciousness

Public awareness increasingly influences consumer markets, with changing perceptions likely to affect purchasing behaviours. Investigative reporting has raised alarms about the health risks of PFAS exposure through everyday products, contributing to heightened consumer consciousness. Consumer advocacy groups have played an important role in raising awareness about PFAS in consumer products as they push for stricter regulations and clearer labelling requirements, addressing the lack of transparency on PFAS-related risks (Cousins et al., 2019).

Generally, there is heightened demand for transparency and accountability regarding the chemicals in products and operations. Some companies are responding by increasing transparency about their products or phasing out the use of PFAS entirely. Furthermore, this trend has also opened up the space for start-ups, using sustainability and transparency as their main selling point. This trend toward increased transparency empowers consumers to make informed choices and fuels demand for safer alternatives that are free of PFAS. As a result, markets for such products are growing, offering opportunities for companies that can meet these expectations.

Trust erosion

According to the Eurobarometer survey *Attitudes of Europeans towards the Environment* (2020), 84% of Europeans express concern about chemicals in everyday products impacting their health, and 90% worry about their effects on the environment. Widespread PFAS contamination and its health risks is often seen as a reason for eroding public trust in the chemical industry. Scandals involving corporate misconduct, such as withholding critical health data, have severely damaged the industry's reputation (Gaber et al., 2023). As a result, the handling of PFAS-related issues by major chemical companies has heightened scepticism about corporate accountability and the effectiveness of self-regulation (Onencan et al., 2024).

Some analysts suggest that these controversies are beginning to affect stock market valuations for major chemical firms. Simultaneously, opportunities exist for new entrants or proactive companies within the industry to rebuild trust. Demonstrating commitment to environmental and public health concerns through transparency, innovation, and accountability could reshape public perception and create competitive advantages.

For the BIO-SUSHY value chain, the increasing public awareness and trust challenges associated with PFAS show that the growing demand for transparency and accountability provides critical momentum for bio-based alternatives like BIO-SUSHY's coatings.

- By addressing concerns about environmental and health risks, these sustainable solutions can help (re-)build consumer trust and meet the rising expectations for safer, PFAS-free products.
- As markets shift towards transparency-driven purchasing behavior, BIO-SUSHY coatings have the potential to position themselves as a credible, eco-friendly alternative aligned with consumer and regulatory trends.

2.3. Setting 3: Regulatory developments

Summary:

- The EU has a comparatively strong reputation when it comes to the protection of its citizens against harmful chemicals, most prominently under REACH
- Recent developments define contextual conditions of regulation, most notably the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability with its emphasis on a “toxic-free environment”
- A group of EU states has come up with an ECHA restriction proposal for a general ban on PFAS
- Depending on successfulness, mentioned restriction proposal will likely have decisive implications on the need for PFAS alternatives

The EU has a comparatively strong reputation when it comes to protecting its citizens from adverse effects of chemical pollution and toxicity. A pivotal role is played by regulatory frameworks, such as the REACH Regulation (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals) and the Classification, Labelling, and Packaging Regulation (CLP). These kinds of regulations enforce strict limits on hazardous substances, require extensive safety testing, and promote transparency in the use of chemicals. Additionally, the EU's current commitment to initiatives like SSbD are anticipated to reinforce its proactive approach to minimising risks while fostering innovation in safer alternatives.

Regulatory developments and existing measures

With the growing awareness of environmental persistence and health risks, efforts to regulate PFAS have intensified. Whereas academics and civil society actors increasingly call for an immediate ban, addressing PFAS remains challenging due to their pervasive use across industries. Current regulations have tackled specific subsets of PFAS over the years, providing a foundation for broader actions. Notably, in 2006 the EU restricted the marketing and use of perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) under the Dangerous Substances Directive, a restriction later incorporated into the REACH Regulation. Also, in 2009, PFOS was designated as a Persistent Organic Pollutant (POP) targeted for elimination under the Stockholm Convention, followed by perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) addition to the POPs list in 2019. Both PFOS and PFOA are subject to restrictions under the POPs Regulation as well.

Furthermore, there are existing restrictions on PFAS in specific products. For instance, under the EU Drinking Water Directive (2020/2184/EU), specific limits have been set for PFAS levels in drinking water. By 2023, Member States had to implement thresholds for the sum of certain PFAS and for total PFAS content, with enforcement measures taking full effect by January 2026. Another important example are food contact materials, where the EU has established maximum allowable levels of key

PFAS, such as PFOS and PFOA, under Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006, supplemented by guidelines on sampling and analysis in Commission Implementation Regulation (EU) 2022/1428. These rules help ensure food safety by monitoring PFAS levels in products like packaging. Furthermore, regarding pollution, the EU restricts PFAS in various applications under specific regulations. For instance, firefighting foams containing PFAS are heavily controlled, with the EU introducing measures in 2021 to phase out PFAS-based foams.

Toward comprehensive PFAS regulation

Despite its comparatively robust regulatory framework, chemical pollution in (Western) Europe is often considered to be comparatively high. Factors that contribute are the area's dense population, its heavy industrial activity. A shift toward more comprehensive PFAS regulation is now underway, marked by a growing consensus among policymakers and regulators. In 2023, Denmark, Germany, the Netherlands, Norway, and Sweden proposed a European ban targeting the entire PFAS class. The proposal represents one of the most ambitious global efforts to tackle the challenges of these persistent chemicals. Recognising the limitations of regulating individual substances within the vast PFAS class—comprising over 10,000 chemicals—the proposal aims to restrict the entire category. A pivotal motivation behind the proposal's comprehensive character is PFAS persistence and the uncertainty created by insufficient testing, warranting a precautionary approach to restrict the entire class (nicely visualised in Figure 5 from the EEA).

For PFAS as a group we have limited knowledge

Figure 5: Limited knowledge as a pivotal argument for comprehensive PFAS regulation. Source: (Thorpe & European Environmental Bureau, 2024)

This approach is designed to prevent *regrettable substitution*, where banned chemicals are replaced by structurally or functionally similar alternatives that later reveal equivalent risks. Under the EU's REACH framework, the ban would apply broadly across most industrial and consumer uses of PFAS, with exemptions permitted only for essential applications where no safer alternatives exist and the

benefits outweigh the risks. Such exceptions are likely to include sectors such as healthcare and certain high-performance industrial contexts.

Implementation is expected to happen in a gradual manner, with an important role for the alternatives and their availability (RIVM, 2023). While the phased strategy allows industries reliant on PFAS more time to adapt, critics caution that delays could exacerbate environmental contamination and health risks. The proposal reflects a careful balancing act, acknowledging the economic and logistical challenges for industry while addressing the urgency of mitigating PFAS-related harm. By prioritising early intervention, proponents argue, the regulation can accelerate innovation, driving the development of safer, PFAS-free technologies and creating new market opportunities.

Proactive regulation and industry adaptation

Much work remains to ensure a balance between public health priorities, industrial innovation, and environmental protection. The regulatory landscape must continue to evolve, fostering a future where safer and more sustainable alternatives replace harmful substances effectively. These regulatory efforts align with the EU's broader Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) and its goal of a toxic-free environment under the European Green Deal. By targeting PFAS, the initiative signals the EU's leadership in proactive chemical regulation, offering a model for tackling persistent pollutants worldwide. The proposed ban not only emphasises protecting public health and the environment but also demonstrates how robust regulatory frameworks can catalyse systemic change in industry practices. If successful, it could pave the way for similar initiatives in other jurisdictions, underscoring the EU's role in setting global standards for sustainability and safety.

As becomes clear, the path to effective PFAS regulation is not without its challenges. Nevertheless, there is an obvious need for thorough hazard assessments of proposed alternatives. For instance, a 2015 report from the Danish Ministry of the Environment underscores that in the recent past, many alternatives for long-chain PFAS, particularly in food packaging, have either replicated the risks of short-chain PFAS or lack sufficient hazard data (Jesper Kjølholt et al., 2015). To address these kinds of challenges, policymakers and industry stakeholders are increasingly advocating for a precautionary approach. This involves robust pre-market evaluations of alternatives, greater transparency in hazard profiles, and investments in non-chemical solutions where feasible. Such measures are critical to breaking the cycle of substitution and ensuring that regulatory frameworks effectively mitigate long-term risks. In this way, industry responses are ideally evolving in tandem with regulatory developments. In that regard, companies need to become increasingly proactive, leveraging chemical testing, certification, and advisory services to align with emerging standards.

For the BIO-SUSHY value chain, the EU's proactive approach, including the proposed PFAS ban, underscores the urgency of developing safe and sustainable alternatives.

- BIO-SUSHY coatings can leverage this shift by aligning with stringent regulations and demonstrating compliance with emerging standards through the development of its SSbD approach.
- By prioritising transparency and innovation, safe and sustainable solutions can position themselves as forward-thinking alternatives, meeting both regulatory demands and market expectations for safer, PFAS-free products.

2.4. Setting 4: Trends in chemicals, coatings, and new materials sectors

Summary:

- Industry developments, combined with regulatory changes are seen as pivotal for the transition towards PFAS substitutes
- Apart from the PFAS issue, the EU's chemical industry finds itself in a challenging position due to macro-economic and geopolitical pressures
- Overnight success is difficult in the chemical industry: new products are often in development for more than a decade, often without yielding profits during that period
- A transformative vision for the future can propel already existing long-term research on bio-based chemicals, and help the development of new R&D programs
- In a positive scenario, the PFAS phase-out can go hand-in-hand with innovative, bio-based alternatives

At this moment, the different approaches towards PFAS restriction in different legislatures create a rather complex situation for producers and retailers that aim to reduce their chemical footprint. Combined with the rise in consumer awareness of PFAS issues and the associated brand reputation, a proactive attitude focused on the phase out PFAS is becoming increasingly common.

The business climate around PFAS

Companies that are considering phasing out PFAS can do so for a variety of reasons ranging from framing themselves as part of (high-end) bio-based consumer markets, to anticipating the implementation of future restrictive regulations. Furthermore, some companies prepare for a situation in which the case of PFAS causes considerable liability exposure. This demonstrates that PFAS is becoming a major legal and financial risk which can harm involved companies substantially.

As a result, chemical firms are under increasing pressure from investors to speed up the removal of highly hazardous chemicals from their product lists. For instance, in December 2022, a letter from 47 top global institutional investors, managing \$8 trillion in assets, including AXA, Aviva, Credit Suisse Asset Management, Resona and Robeco, was presented to more than 50 major chemical companies. These investors called for greater transparency regarding the production of (hazardous) chemicals. The letter has a specific focus on PFAS, encouraging the CEOs of the biggest chemical companies to "lead, not be led, by phasing out and substituting these chemicals" (Perkins, 2023). In direct connection to this letter, the Investor Initiative on Hazardous Chemicals (IIHC) was established in February 2023, with the -Sweden-based- NGO ChemSec as the coordinator of the initiative (ChemSec, 2024).

These kinds of efforts to enhance transparency often focus on disclosing information about the production and use of hazardous chemicals, including their presence in products and their associated economic impacts. Such approaches typically emphasise the need for clear, time-bound plans to phase out persistent substances like PFAS. They also help underline the importance of increasing investments in the development of safer alternatives, highlighting the potential for long-term value creation through these advancements.

Sustainability-driven transitions away from PFAS

Phasing out PFAS and finding (bio-based) alternatives requires new innovations. It is useful to point at developments in this industry that can help to understand the broader context of how sustainable and safer chemicals are being developed. Examining these trends can help gain insight into the strategies and technologies that will drive the future of chemical manufacturing towards a more sustainable paradigm. By embracing sustainability, chemical companies can align their vision with the evolving needs of society while securing their future competitiveness and resilience.

A range of different measures that can help achieve this have been suggested, optimisation of supply chains for resilience, fostering sustainable innovation through research and development, and fostering collaboration among a wide group of stakeholders. By implementing a holistic approach encompassing these strategies, industry actors can mitigate the impact of rising energy costs and navigate towards a more sustainable and competitive future. Nevertheless, this needs to get more clearly defined in many different domains of the chemical industry. In that regard, the phasing out of PFAS in a wide range of (consumer) products and its replacement by bio-based alternatives should be seen as a lighthouse example for a wider transition. This focus on responsible innovation fosters collaboration across the industry, from partnerships with research institutions to engagement with stakeholders, ensuring that the shift away from PFAS and toward biobased alternatives is both effective and holistic.

Bioeconomy and the EU chemical industry

Finally, the concept of bioeconomy already offers a transformative vision that integrates economic growth with environmental sustainability and social responsibility. By transitioning from a fossil fuel-based economy to one that relies on renewable biological resources, the bioeconomy reduces dependence on non-renewable materials through innovations like plant-based plastics, biodegradable polymers, and bio-based chemicals. This shift not only optimises resource use but also aligns with circular economy principles by promoting recycling, reuse, and waste reduction (Cefic, 2022).

Renewable biological resources, including agricultural residues, forestry waste, algae, and organic by-products, provide sustainable alternatives to traditional raw materials. Adopting integrated approaches that consider the interconnections between food, energy, and environmental systems can help optimise resource use and minimise trade-offs between food security and other societal needs. For instance, prioritising non-food biomass helps address concerns about food security by minimising competition with food production. Further, advances in biotechnology and agricultural practices further enhance crop yields and resource efficiency, enabling the cultivation of biomass for industrial use without compromising food availability.

For the chemical and materials industry, bio-based processes open opportunities for developing safer, non-toxic alternatives to hazardous substances, addressing regulatory pressures and consumer demand for sustainable products. Innovations in bio-based composites and coatings, bear promise to provide durable, environmentally friendly solutions that meet performance standards while reducing reliance on finite raw materials. Ultimately, the bioeconomy strengthens long-term value creation by fostering innovation, reducing environmental risks, and contributing to sustainable development goals, including climate resilience, food security, and resource efficiency.

For the BIO-SUSHY value chain, the transition away from PFAS and toward bio-based alternatives aligns with broader trends in sustainability and industry transformation.

- Industry pressure to phase out hazardous chemicals reinforces the need for scalable, PFAS-free coatings.
- Aligning with ESG-driven innovation can enhance market positioning and investment opportunities.
- Bioeconomy and circular economy strategies support the development and adoption of sustainable coatings.

2.5. Setting 5: EU R&I policy for industry growth and sustainability

Summary:

- EU strategic plans are pushing towards strategic autonomy, while focusing on issues like circularity, climate-neutrality and sustainability
- EU strategy is a necessary building block in the development towards a sustainable chemical industry that establishes new vision for growth
- BIO-SUSHY success can help to further establish the vision of a sustainable chemical industry
- Several concepts and strategies propelled by the EU are currently in a phase where they can either gain or lose momentum, e.g. its CSS, the SSbD concept, and its Bioeconomy plans.

Research and innovation policies play a critical role in driving the development and adoption of safer alternatives to PFAS, fostering research, funding, and collaboration across industries. By supporting scalable solutions, these policies can accelerate the transition away from PFAS, reducing environmental and health risks while ensuring sustainable industrial practices. Furthermore, it is also useful to place this in the context of the broader sustainability transition, which is increasingly becoming a primary (geo)political and economic incentive. In that context, large-scale efforts such as green industrial policies are used in order to ‘win’ the green transition. Policies focused on fostering growth and innovation as well as policies that aim for transitions towards a sustainable economy and society.

Sustainability and industry growth

Historically, the chemical and materials sectors have been pillars of the EU economy, offering high-skilled employment and maintaining strong international competitiveness. However, recent challenges, including rising energy costs linked to the EU energy transition, COVID-19 supply chain disruptions, and geopolitical instability from the war in Ukraine, have created significant obstacles. The combination of these factors have created a challenging environment for European industry, impacting competitiveness and profitability. To escape a detrimental cycle of dwindling revenues combined with lack of strategic direction and a lack of investment, there is a widespread sense that European industry needs to take proactive steps for establishing clear long-term visions and strategic plans to drive a new wave of innovations.

Furthermore, the CSS is a policy framework aimed at balancing economic imperatives with environmental goals. While the CSS primarily addresses regulatory and safety standards, its innovation policy component supports a transition toward sustainable industrial practices, aligning with broader EU ambitions. These policies form a cornerstone in the EU's broader strategic plan, focusing on achieving circularity, climate neutrality, and sustainability. Beyond immediate regulatory goals, they represent a necessary building block for new industrial visions centered on sustainable growth. Initiatives like BIO-SUSHY exemplify the EU's efforts to foster leadership in the development of a sustainable chemical industry, showcasing how targeted innovation can drive broader industrial transformation.

Figure 6: The CSS toxic-free hierarchy as envisioned by the European Commission. Source: (European Commission, 2020)

PFAS substitution as an industrial strategy

Transitioning away from PFAS represents a significant technical and strategic challenge for industries reliant on their unique properties. In the past, substitution efforts have often resulted in incremental improvements without fully mitigating environmental and health risks. The EU is currently making efforts to respond with a comprehensive lifecycle approach, emphasising sustainability at every stage of production. In this context, industrial strategies that prioritise building resilient, sustainable supply chains that leverage international collaboration while supporting local bioeconomies. Such efforts aim to overcome challenges in scaling up bio-based alternatives and reducing dependence on fossil-based resources.

Initiatives like the EU Bioeconomy Strategy and Circular Economy Action Plan further underline the importance of fostering innovation, reducing waste, and promoting renewable resources to drive long-term industrial transformation. These plans not only address immediate challenges but also contribute to achieving strategic autonomy in key industrial domains. By embedding bioeconomy principles into industrial strategy, the EU ensures alignment with its broader sustainability goals while maintaining competitiveness on the global stage.

SSbD as a strategy for innovation

The EU's SSbD framework plays a pivotal role in the transition to a sustainable chemical industry. Unlike regulatory measures that focus solely on compliance, SSbD also provides a forward-looking approach to designing chemicals and materials with minimal environmental and health impacts throughout their lifecycle. This framework is instrumental in fostering innovation, not only in bio-based coatings but also in defining standards for sustainable product design.

By embedding SSbD principles, the EU aims to enhance the learning curve in sustainable innovation, ensuring that new materials and technologies meet environmental and performance criteria. This approach complements efforts to replace hazardous substances, like PFAS, with safer alternatives, addressing both technical challenges and broader sustainability goals. The emphasis on SSbD aligns closely with EU strategic efforts, such as the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, to solidify its leadership in the global green transition. These initiatives are at a critical juncture, requiring consistent momentum to realise their potential and ensure the EU's position as a leader in sustainable industrial practices. Furthermore, Horizon Europe provides a strategic platform for advancing these goals, aligning research and innovation efforts with broader industrial and environmental objectives.

For the BIO-SUSHY value chain, the EU's push for strategic autonomy and sustainability strengthens the case for bio-based coatings as key solutions in the chemical industry transition.

- Aligning with SSbD principles and EU innovation strategies can help enhance BIO-SUSHY's market positioning.
- Engaging with EU bioeconomy and circular economy initiatives can support future scalability and industrial integration.
- Leveraging Horizon Europe and policy-driven funding can accelerate the development of PFAS alternatives.

3. Challenges & opportunities in BIO-SUSHY value chains

After considering broader socioeconomic issues and sustainability objectives, the challenges and opportunities regarding the specific value chains of BIO-SUSHY solutions are to be discussed. For each of the BIO-SUSHY value chains, this section delves into pivotal factors shaping the landscape, addressing key dimensions for each of them.

Considerations regarding TRL

TRL has already been mentioned as an important factor in the considerations. For this section the issue is particularly relevant, since it dives deeper into each of the value chains. At this point, midway through the project, solutions are expected to have a TRL of approximately 3 to 4. This means the solution has reached the stage where it is validated in a lab environment. At this point, the value chain is by definition preliminary. For instance, raw suppliers may be identified for the lab-stage solution, but can change when sourcing takes place for production on a bigger scale. Manufacturing processes are usually still largely conceptual, with activities focusing on pilot production, but still subject to change as well. Distribution channels are still to be developed further, since the focus remains on testing and refinement of the technology behind the BIO-SUSHY solutions. Finally, sustainability factors cannot always be addressed in a detailed manner at this stage, since the main priority is to prove the technical feasibility of the solutions. In summary, the value chains are in a nascent stage, awaiting further technological maturation.

Towards the end of the project, BIO-SUSHY solutions are expected to have a TRL of 5 to 6, solutions are expected to be validated in their respective contexts. Typically, they are mostly based on prototype testing to allow further exploitation, with both internal and (potential) external partners using state of the art technologies to validate the coatings applicability in each value chain. Suppliers might begin sourcing materials, but the supply chain is likely far from optimised yet. In terms of manufacturing, it is likely that pilot production processes will be in place, but they will not yet be scalable, nor are they expected to be highly efficient. Also when it comes to distribution channels, they are likely still in an exploratory or at best in an early developmental phase, and it is not unlikely that they are placed outside of the BIO-SUSHY consortium (e.g. at clients of BIO-SUSHY partners). Sustainability considerations might also be underway, though full integration into the value chain is not expected to be completed.

Approach

Taking these considerations into account, the approach taken in this section is more forward-looking (or provisional), focusing on potential developments and likely scenarios for how the value chain might evolve as the technology matures. This provides insights into future possibilities rather than a definitive assessment of the current state. The main themes in this regard are to focus on enriching the compatibility with industrial applications in each of the solution's value chain, based on three criteria, estimate assessments of use case requirements, and finally to implement safety and sustainability considerations in the current and future stages of the value chains. More specifically, for each of the cases the following considerations are provided:

- Introduction of the broader market context of the respective value chain
- Summary of substitution & sustainability priorities in the respective value chain
- Innovation opportunities and value chain considerations for the BIO-SUSHY solution
- Priorities for establishing sustainable, safe, and transparent value chains

3.1. Disposable paper food packaging coatings

Introduction

The food packaging market is vast, covering a wide variety of products and needs. In essence, most food packaging serves two primary functions: first, it preserves food safety, quality, and shelf life. Second, packaging plays a key role as a communication tool, helping to capture consumer attention and reinforce brand identity. Also, it provides essential information, including ingredients, nutritional facts, usage instructions, and certifications, thus helping to build consumer trust and influencing purchasing decisions.

The future of packaging is deeply tied to questions of sustainability and safety. While current packaging practices offer clear benefits in terms of food protection and cost efficiency, they also raise widely recognised concerns. Single-use plastic packaging, which has long been the leading packaging material, is widely recognised for its issues with regards to environmental sustainability, toxicity, waste, and pollution (including microplastics). Although efforts to improve sustainability often target single-use plastics, it remains the dominant food packaging solution today. There are several types of solutions that hold promise in multi-use packaging solutions (e.g. glass), but these often come with substantial logistical challenges. For alternative solutions in the domain of single-use packaging, paper packaging has long been the leading alternative to plastic due to its image of biodegradability and recyclability.

However, paper packaging also has major environmental and health challenges that are often caused or exacerbated by the use of PFAS-based coatings. An example of such a pressing concern is consumer safety, as substances can leach into food, posing potential health risks. Environmental leaching of these harmful substances during disposal or recycling processes can also lead to broader contamination, affecting ecosystems and water supplies. The BIO-SUSHY solution addresses these challenges by developing bio-based coatings that not only eliminate harmful substances but also meet the performance standards required for food safety and packaging functionality, paving the way for safer and more sustainable solutions.

Safety and sustainability priorities in the value chain

This section provides a summary of the relevant key challenges and priorities within the disposable paper food packaging value chain. The focus here is to describe the impacts of current practices and the way these challenges can help establish a way forward for the BIO-SUSHY SSbD approach to building its value chains.

Impacts and hazards of current packaging solutions

In paper packaging, the safety issue is the most obvious priority when it comes to the need for substitution. PFAS coatings in paper food packaging have been widely used since the 1970s, particularly for fast food, takeout, and convenience items, seeing a sharp rise in application through the early 2000s. As a result, production processes for PFAS-based coatings are entrenched within the paper packaging industry, relying on chemical formulations and techniques that have been optimised over decades. As a result, the chemicals persist in production waste streams, contaminating water supplies and ecosystems. Also, the presence of PFAS in food packaging coatings has become a significant health concern in recent years. Studies show that PFAS can migrate into food, especially under conditions like high heat or prolonged storage. For instance, a coalition of European organisations found PFAS in 32 out of 42 food packaging samples analysed from fast food chains across six EU countries (Straková et al., 2021). This migration leads to direct dietary exposure, which is considered one of the primary routes of PFAS accumulation in humans. Some of these compounds are known to bioaccumulate, underscoring the urgent need for alternatives.

There are also significant concerns around the unintended presence of PFAS chemicals in food packaging production. Recent investigations have found that the lion's share of chemicals in packaging are not authorised by regulatory bodies (Phelps et al., 2024). These kinds of mismatches suggest that impurities, degradation products, or unregulated variants could be introduced during the manufacturing process. These unintended chemicals may result from the breakdown of long-chain PFAS into shorter variants during production or from contamination across supply chains (Bourzac, 2024). This makes compliance with regulatory frameworks more challenging, complicating efforts to ensure that the raw materials used for food packaging meet safety standards. A clear challenge here is that a considerable share of identified chemicals in packaging lack publicly available hazard data, resulting in the fact that manufacturers often face challenges in assessing and mitigating risks during procurement.

Increasing pressure to improve recycling possibilities

Apart from the health related issues, PFAS-coated paper packaging poses significant challenges for recycling systems. These coatings are difficult to separate from the paper fibers, limiting the ability to effectively recycle or reuse the material. When PFAS-coated packaging is discarded, it often contributes to landfill leachate and incineration emissions. Studies have shown that PFAS persist in landfill environments, leaching into soil and groundwater, and standard incineration processes fail to fully break down the chemicals, dispersing them into the atmosphere. This pollution has been documented near waste incinerators in Europe, where elevated PFAS levels were found in ecosystems, highlighting the long-term risks associated with these materials.

As a result, despite being recyclable in principle, paper packaging often ends up in landfills due to contamination from food residues and composite materials like plastic or aluminum layers. These mixed materials complicate the recycling process, as they are hard to separate and clean, reducing the efficiency and quality of recycled fibers. This is an important reason for the fact that according to Eurostat estimates, paper packaging in the EU currently accounts for the largest portion of landfill

waste (see Figure 7), with limited pathways for effective reuse, undermining its environmental benefits.

Packaging waste generated, by packaging material, EU, 2022
(%)

Note: Eurostat estimates.

Source: Eurostat (online data code: env_waspac)

eurostat

Figure 7: Eurostat's estimates of packaging waste generated by packaging material in 2022.

Regulatory & legal exposure

Finally, mentioned concerns around PFAS increase regulatory and legal exposure, establishing itself as a key driver behind the pressure in the paper packaging value chain to implement new coatings that fulfil more stringent substitution and sustainability requirements. Food packaging coatings are one of the most prominent examples where the use of PFAS is often considered avoidable, particularly since key markets with stricter regulations have already proven that viable alternatives can emerge. For instance, Denmark's 2020 ban on PFAS in cardboard and paper food contact materials demonstrated that companies are able to adapt. Across Europe, increasing awareness of the environmental and health risks posed by PFAS has led to an evolving regulatory landscape, particularly focused on restricting these substances in food packaging.

These evolving bans and restrictions put pressure on both raw material suppliers and producers in the paper packaging industry to find safer alternatives. Also, especially in the U.S., lawsuits have already been filed against major food brands and retailers for misleading advertising, product liability, and failure to warn, particularly where PFAS contamination undermines claims of purity,

naturalness, or compostability (BCLP Law, 2023). Some of these high-profile cases have targeted fast food chains, grocery stores, and manufacturers of disposable packaging, alleging that PFAS presence makes food unfit for consumption. These cases highlight the increasing scrutiny, amplifying the demand for safer and more transparent alternatives throughout the value chain.

Apart from the developments regarding a general ban on PFAS, the EU's Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation reflects growing urgency in the packaging domain. Furthermore, existing regulations, such as the EU Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC) and the Regulation on Materials and Articles Intended to Come into Contact with Food (EC 1935/2004), emphasise the reduction of hazardous substances in products and the promotion of sustainable materials. However, PFAS poses unique challenges that these frameworks are only beginning to address fully. Also broader objectives of EU directives like the Single-Use Plastics Directive (2019/904) encourage the development of biodegradable and recyclable alternatives. PFAS contamination complicates recycling processes, undermining the circular economy goals outlined in the Circular Economy Action Plan (2020). Finally, further pressure comes from member states pushing forward their own regulations to phase out PFAS, with countries such as Denmark and Germany already implementing stricter measures.

Relevant priorities for BIO-SUSHY

- The substitution of PFAS, with safer, more sustainable alternatives is a key priority in the paper food packaging market. Alternatives should eliminate/minimise health impacts & environmental contamination.
- Need for high-performing, sustainable alternatives that maintain barrier properties against grease and moisture. Switching to alternative coatings necessitates a systemic overhaul, a process that is likely to be resource-intensive and disruptive.
- Coatings should become more compatible with paper recycling systems, reducing contamination and improving end-of-life sustainability. Ultimately they need to align with circular economy goals.
- Organic powder coatings as developed in BIO-SUSHY would address additional End of Life (EoL) like compostability involving current ISO standards.
- Reliance on PFAS-coated paper in food packaging coatings already perpetuates uncertainty, regulatory non-compliance, and potential liability. Bio-based coatings can ensure regulatory compliance, and minimise liability risks by aligning with evolving environmental and regulatory standards.
- A new generation of transparent, credible materials have the potential to foster trust and set new standards for safety and sustainability in food packaging.
- There is a clear need for products and processes that are future-proof. New solutions should anticipate regulatory trends, enabling long-term compliance and positioning the value chain for sustainability leadership.

BIO-SUSHY innovation opportunities and value chain considerations

Efforts to eliminate PFAS in the paper food packaging value chain generally have a strong focus on bio-based and biodegradable coatings to replace PFAS in food contact materials. The main goal here is to develop alternatives that offer similar water and oil resistance but avoid the environmental and health impact. Research and development are particularly active in the paper and cardboard sectors, where plant-based and biodegradable coatings are being tested to replace PFAS in fast-food and takeout packaging. Lignin-based coatings using different lignin types are available at pre-commercial scale while also bio-based waxes have shown promise, where achieving comparable grease and water resistance is a key priority.

In that regard, the BIO-SUSHY solution demonstrates promising potential. BIO-SUSHY's innovative bio-based food packaging coatings are designed to address both functionality and sustainability challenges in the food packaging value chain. Its lignin-based coatings fulfill water repellency and water uptake criteria, with future formulations being optimised to avoid leakage. Moreover, developments in terms of grease resistance are showing promising results. Further enhancing its appeal, the coating's objectives include improving recycling compatibility and enhancing the durability of paper-based packaging while minimising its environmental footprint. Beyond BIO-SUSHY, scaling this solution and tailoring the performance of these types of coatings is possible based on specific packaging needs. As such, these innovations have clear potential to help bridge the gap between lab-scale development and industrial application. This customisation adds to its promise as a solution that is ideal for a wide range of food packaging applications, providing the potential to reduce the environmental footprint of packaging materials.

BIO-SUSHY solution:

Biobased powder coating (Wood K plus)	formulation content >80% biobased	90-100% organic	0% solvent (powder coating)	Powder spray application; Gelling temperatures: 80 to max. 200 °C; Gelling time: 5 to 30 sec.
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- Coating solution is based on lignin combined with biodegradable, partly bio-based, non-toxic plastics: polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHBV) and polybutylene succinate (PBS).
- Coatings are applied onto different paper substrates suitable for the hot forming process. Besides, selected formulations will be tested on cellulosic material (pulp mat + tissue papers) to demonstrate the potential wider applications of developed coatings.
- Electrostatic spray coating is being used as an application technology onto paper followed by hot pressing - s film formation upon applying temperature. Coated paper is further thermoformed into a 3D shape (supporting innovation in design flexibility).
- After cooling, the coated papers are thermoformed using a Novatec PV10-5010 PLUS blank feeding machine (in close cooperation with an end user).

Achieving systemic improvements in safety, sustainability, and fairness in paper packaging requires tackling challenges at multiple stages, from sourcing to production to disposal. These different priorities can complicate communication among stakeholders on potential solutions. The following analysis will clarify these issues and examine BIO-SUSHY's changes and contributions toward transforming the food packaging market and its value chains.

Raw materials & sourcing

The BIO-SUSHY coating solution is based on lignin natural polymer combined with biodegradable, bio-based, non-toxic plastics: PHBV and PBS. Carnauba wax is tested as an additive to enhance barrier properties.

Lignin

Lignin is a complex organic polymer found in plant cell walls. It provides structural support, rigidity, and resistance to degradation. Its properties make it valuable for sustainable applications, including bioplastics, adhesives, carbon fiber, and functional coatings, offering a promising alternative to petroleum-based materials. In industrial contexts, technical lignin is primarily a by-product of pulping and biorefinery industries, where most of it is burned for energy rather than being utilised in high-value applications. Further, lignin from the upcoming cellulosic ethanol industry is becoming significant. Both chemical and physical treatments cause changes in lignin in terms of structure, molecular weight distribution and dispersity. Thus lignin availability and related price is impacted by the production process, its purity and functionality.

The production of Kraft lignin is resource- and energy-intensive, with implications for the environmental footprint of lignin-based products. While modern recovery systems and advancements in air filtration and effluent treatment have mitigated these impacts, the Kraft process remains a source of emissions and environmental challenges. Furthermore, the sustainability of lignin, as well as of the cellulosic fibres in the trays, relies on responsible forest management. BIO-SUSHY currently sources purified kraft softwood lignin from suppliers committed to sustainable practices. While the wood fibers in paper packaging are not part of the coating, both coatings and fibers depend on sustainable forestry. Practices like replanting, biodiversity maintenance, and adherence to standards like the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) or the Programme for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) ensure legal sourcing and preserve forests as carbon sinks. On the other hand, unsustainable practices can lead to deforestation and biodiversity loss, offsetting lignin's carbon benefits. Europe's sustainable forestry efforts have expanded forest cover over the past decades, but challenges like biodiversity loss and climate change require localised strategies and further improvements of certification schemes to ensure sustainability.

Finally, for advanced applications like coatings, lignin must meet high-purity standards and safety measures being addressed. In some cases, this can form a significant barrier, because refining lignin to these specifications can be technologically and economically challenging. These processes, which often involve purification, chemical modification, are energy-intensive and innovations are important to further improve sustainability. Nevertheless, recent years show developments into a direction where lignin-based solutions are increasingly able to compete with other types of

solutions. Scaling these innovations will ultimately be vital for achieving cost efficiency and environmental gains.

Bio-based Polymers (PHBV & PBS)

The BIO-SUSHY solution uses bio-based polymers like Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) in different types and Poly Butylene Succinate (PBS). PHAs and PBS are bio-based polymers that can replace traditional petroleum-derived materials, and when combined with lignin they can contribute to a more circular economy by repurposing waste materials. PBS is typically derived from renewable resources such as plant sugars. The production of PBS often involves the fermentation of sugar substrates, such as glucose, derived from crops like corn or sugarcane. PHAs are also produced through fermentation, where specific bacteria synthesise the polymer from carbon sources like sugars or lipids. These sources are typically derived from plant-based biomass or waste products from the food industry, further enhancing PHAs sustainability.

Since PBS and PHAs are products of biological synthesis, they are inherently bio-based and biodegradable, and can be produced using industrial waste streams such as agricultural residues or food byproducts, which makes them attractive options in terms of circularity. Nevertheless, the environmental impact of sourcing the raw materials, such as land use for growing crops, must also be considered in assessing the overall sustainability of PBS production. Other issues to consider are the energy used in production particularly in PHAs fermentation process, and the overall lifecycle of the materials. Nevertheless, the use of these biopolymers reduces the reliance on fossil fuels, thus lowering the environmental impact of packaging.

Furthermore, one of the key advantages of these biopolymers is their biodegradability. This helps mitigate the growing issue of plastic waste, providing a sustainable solution that aligns better with global efforts to reduce environmental harm. Both PHAs and PBS are compostable PHAs even considering different conditions and environments, which means that their use in paper coatings provides an environmentally friendly alternative to conventional plastic-based coatings. The incorporation of lignin further strengthens the biodegradability without compromising bio-based content of the total formulation, making the coatings an even more sustainable option for food packaging.

Carnauba wax

Carnauba wax has potential in new biobased coatings for paper packaging due to its natural hydrophobic properties and biodegradability. Carnauba wax is derived from the leaves of the *Copernicia prunifera* palm, a tree that thrives in arid regions and is native to northeastern Brazil. It presents a potentially useful component for eco-friendly alternatives to PFAS-based coatings. The harvesting process involves pruning the leaves to collect the wax without damaging the trees. In principle this ensures continued production while preserving the palms and their surrounding ecosystems. Unlike synthetic alternatives, carnauba wax is biodegradable, non-toxic, and does not contribute to long-term pollution. Additionally, it is compatible with other biopolymers, enhancing coating durability and performance for food-safe applications.

The production of carnauba wax has faced scrutiny due to labour exploitation and environmental challenges. Reports reveal that some workers in carnauba plantations endure poor conditions, including lack of safety equipment, long hours, and low wages. The informality in the sector worsens these issues, since it makes accountability difficult despite efforts to enforce better practices. However, initiatives like the [Initiative for Responsible Carnauba \(IRC\)](#) are driving improvements. Established in 2018, the IRC involves Brazilian wax processors, international buyers, and NGOs working to ensure labour rights, ethical sourcing, and biodiversity conservation. Commitments under this initiative include audits, third-party verifications, and sourcing standards.

Production & processing

Lignin-based coatings hold promise for improving sustainability and reducing reliance on unsafe materials. Achieving consistency, scalability, and cost-effectiveness in industrial applications remains a work in progress which is fully dependent on the market pull (Dessbesell et al., 2020). Addressing these issues is essential for realising the full potential of lignin as a key material for biobased food packaging (Straits Research, 2024).

Consistency & uniformity

Lignin's complex and variable structure makes it difficult to process uniformly. In industrial production, consistency and uniformity are often essential. This presents a significant challenge for lignin-based coatings. Lignin, as a natural polymer derived from various plant sources, has a complex and variable structure that can differ depending on the feedstock and extraction process. This variability can affect the coating's performance, such as its film-forming ability, barrier properties, and adhesion. Ensuring that lignin-based coatings have consistent quality and performance at an industrial scale requires precise control over the composition and properties of lignin, which is not yet fully standardised. Achieving uniformity in lignin production and refining processes is critical to ensuring that these coatings can meet the demands of mass production and compete with well-established alternatives.

In short, lignin holds significant promise for food packaging coatings, but its full potential is still being unlocked as the industry works to optimise both the material's performance and cost-effectiveness. Researchers are currently experimenting with lignin-based resins and composites to develop coatings that can meet or even surpass the performance of petroleum-derived coatings, all while being biodegradable or more environmentally friendly. This potential makes lignin a promising material for the future of biobased coatings, especially in sectors like food packaging

Production costs

Lignin's status as a naturally abundant byproduct of the paper and pulp industry makes it a low-cost, renewable resource with significant potential for replacing petroleum-based materials. However, while raw lignin is inexpensive, converting it into high-performance biobased coatings or bioplastics at commercial scale remains costly due to the need for advanced processing technologies, infrastructure, and ongoing research.

Despite these current barriers, lignin-based coatings offer a promising pathway to reducing costs over time. As technology matures and adoption increases, economies of scale and process efficiencies are expected to lower production costs. This can enhance the viability of lignin-based coatings as a cost-effective, sustainable alternative in the food packaging sector.

Use & application

The BIO-SUSHY coating solution offers significant advancements in barrier properties, food safety, and packaging performance, making it a promising choice for sustainable food packaging applications. These properties are the project's main potential strength, since they are critical for ensuring food remains fresh, safe, and well-protected throughout storage and transportation.

Food safety

Coatings must meet stringent food safety standards to provide a viable alternative to conventional coatings that may leach harmful substances. BIO-SUSHY integrates safety considerations throughout the formulation process, using a combination of laboratory testing and iterative adjustments to minimise potential risks. During R&D, leakage testing is conducted to assess whether any compounds migrate from the coated layer on paper, ensuring that formulations remain safe for food contact. Biomembrane sensor testing helps detect interactions that could indicate unwanted migration, allowing early identification of potential concerns. At later stages, comprehensive migration tests are planned to validate the coatings under real-world conditions, ensuring they comply with regulatory standards for food packaging. This continuous process of evaluation and refinement helps mitigate risks, ensuring that BIO-SUSHY's coatings provide both high performance and consumer safety while reducing potential impacts on human health and the environment.

Packaging quality & structural integrity

Ensuring the quality and structural integrity of food packaging is a critical factor for both consumers and food retailers. For consumers, packaging that fails to protect food can lead to dissatisfaction, food spoilage, and waste. For retailers, compromised packaging can disrupt supply chains, cause product losses, and damage brand reputation. The ability of packaging to withstand handling, transportation, and storage while maintaining its functional and visual properties is therefore essential to its success in the market.

BIO-SUSHY's combination of lignin with biopolymers like PHBV and PBS addresses these challenges by creating coatings with an optimal balance of flexibility and strength. This ensures that paper-based packaging retains its integrity throughout the supply chain while providing the durability needed for demanding environments (e.g. cold storage or extended transportation). The project's use of computational tools and data-driven modeling further supports the design of these coatings, enabling precise prediction and refinement of their physicochemical parameters. Real-world testing in production facilities in close cooperation with end user provides the project with a unique opportunity to confirm that these structural and quality benefits hold up under industrial and commercial conditions.

Certifications & consumer trust

The market is increasingly focused on PFAS-free and bio-based alternatives, and certifications play a critical role in verifying the performance and sustainability of these solutions. Through its toxicological and environmental evaluations, BIO-SUSHY has established methodologies for transparency and standardisation. These tools enhance trust in the project's formulations and position them as credible alternatives that avoid greenwashing while delivering genuine sustainability benefits. In later stages of the project, it is important to increase project-internal awareness of useful certifications and other tools to enhance consumer trust.

Recycling & end-of-life

The BIO-SUSHY solution not only promises to significantly reduce reliance on harmful chemicals but also aims to improve recyclability by reducing the need for non-recyclable components. By integrating seamlessly with paper substrates, lignin-based coatings address key challenges in recycling, such as the separation of plastic or aluminum layers, contributing to the broader goals of a circular economy in the (food) packaging industry.

Enhancing recyclability

Lignin-based coatings improve recyclability by integrating with paper substrates without requiring complex separation processes. Unlike conventional coatings, which often hinder recycling, these bio-based solutions align with the structure of paper fibers, allowing for more efficient recovery. While lignin-based coatings reduce contamination's impact, they do not completely eliminate it. For example, contamination from grease, oils, or food residues remains a challenge that can render batches of paper unsuitable for recycling. However, BIO-SUSHY's protective barrier minimises grease penetration, reducing contamination severity and supporting cleaner recycling streams.

Environmental considerations

While paper-based packaging is celebrated for its recyclability, the process itself can have significant environmental impacts, particularly in terms of water and energy use. Additionally, each recycling cycle shortens cellulose fibres, eventually requiring the addition of virgin fibres to maintain material quality. Thus, to improve on this issue, lignin-based coating developments should focus on support this process by ensuring compatibility with fibre recovery, minimising disruptions in recycling streams. Alternatively, composting provides another end-of-life scenario, particularly for food-soiled packaging that cannot be recycled. Lignin's inherent biodegradability is an advantage in this context, as it naturally breaks down without leaving persistent residues. By developing coatings that balance recyclability with biodegradability, lignin-based solutions can complement existing waste management efforts, ensuring packaging remains sustainable regardless of its disposal route.

Infrastructure challenges & stakeholder involvement

The recyclability of coated materials also depends heavily on the availability of appropriate recycling infrastructure. Even innovative solutions like BIO-SUSHY require facilities capable of recycling or

composting bio-based coatings effectively. Without such infrastructure, the benefits of these coatings may not be fully realised. Continued research and collaboration with recycling stakeholders are essential for aligning material design with real-world recycling capabilities.

Towards a sustainable, safe, and transparent value chain

Sustainability has emerged as a key driver of transformation in the food packaging industry. Companies are increasingly motivated to develop materials, processes, and products that minimise environmental impact, align with evolving regulations, and meet consumer demand for greener solutions. This dynamic landscape has spurred innovation, resulting in advancements like biodegradable packaging and improved recycling technologies. However, the rapid pace of these developments brings the risk of overstated or unverified sustainability claims, which can undermine trust and progress. In summary, two areas define the focus of BIO-SUSHY's solution:

Establishing new standards for sustainability and safety

The approach of combining lignin with biodegradable, bio-based plastics enhances its potential, opening up opportunities to tailor coatings for a wide range of food packaging different segments while meeting regulatory demands for PFAS-free, sustainable solutions. New paper-based packaging solutions exemplify the industry's shift towards sustainability but come with their own challenges. While the BIO-SUSHY solution is not directly engaged in all these dilemmas, its work on the safety and sustainability must remain at the forefront of its activities. Addressing the environmental and safety issues tied to food packaging cannot rely solely on regulation or isolated actions. Project work can help to tackle many current problems, such as reducing harmful additives, promoting mono-material packaging, tackling microplastic dispersion, and refining sorting and recycling methods. Balancing the benefits of such alternatives with their inherent limitations will be critical for achieving sustainable and safe food packaging solutions.

Building trust in new solutions

Single-use food packaging, particularly plastic, has long been associated with environmental harm, and this perception continues to hinder trust in new solutions. Moreover, despite its status as a symbol of waste and pollution, plastic remains the dominant packaging material due to its versatility, durability, and cost-effectiveness. Alternatives often struggle to match its performance on a large scale, making the transition away from plastic a complex challenge. However, this shift is essential for the future of sustainable packaging and requires both innovation and consumer acceptance to make viable alternatives widely adopted.

A key issue in building trust lies in the transparency of sustainability claims. Without verifiable evidence or robust certifications, claims about biodegradability or eco-friendliness can mislead consumers, perpetuating false perceptions of sustainability. This not only undermines progress toward genuine environmental solutions but also erodes consumer confidence, leaving the real environmental impact largely unaddressed. To address this, certification systems can help ensure the overall sustainability of packaging materials.

Disposable paper food packaging coatings

Safety & sustainability priorities in the value chain

Impacts & hazards current solutions

- PFAS migration
- Persistent pollution
- Regulatory gaps

Recycling challenges

- Poor recyclability
- Landfill contamination
- Mixed material issues

Regulatory & legal pressure

- Stricter bans
- Circularity barriers
- Legal & regulatory scrutiny

BIO-SUSHY innovation opportunities and value chain considerations

Raw materials & sourcing

Lignin:
- Structural support
- Pulping by-product
- Sustainable forestry & env. footprint

Bio-based polymers:
- PHAs & PBS
- Industrial waste stream & agri. residue
- Biodegradable

Carnauba wax:
- Tested for hydroph. properties
- Biodegradable, non toxic

Production & processing

Consistency & uniformity of lignin-based coatings important for solution success in production & processing

Production costs likely dependent on maturing technology, economies of scale and improving process efficiencies

Use & application

Coating undergoes rigorous testing to meet **food safety** standards while minimising health and environmental risks.

Packaging quality & structural integrity are important to satisfy both consumer and retailer demands

Certifications & attention to building consumer trust will be pivotal for establishing new coatings solution

Recycling & end-of-life

Lignin:
- Structural support
- Pulping by-product
- Sustainable forestry & env. footprint

Bio-based polymers:
- PHAs & PBS
- Industrial waste stream & agri. residue
- Biodegradable

Carnauba wax:
- Tested for hydroph. properties
- Biodegradable, non toxic

Towards a sustainable, safe, and transparent value chain

BIO-SUSHY needs to clearly frame its contribution to establishing **new standards for sustainability and safety** by developing PFAS-free coatings that reduce harmful additives, support mono-material packaging, and improve recyclability in paper food packaging

To build trust in new solutions, BIO-SUSHY should support transparent sustainability claims and collaborate with certification systems to **ensure credibility and consumer confidence** in PFAS-free alternatives in paper food packaging

3.2. Textile coatings

Introduction

Coatings and their underlying technologies have been pivotal in shaping the modern textile industry. They have enabled manufacturers to engineer fabrics with enhanced properties that cater to a diverse range of needs across industries and for various types of consumers. First of all, these coatings are used in textiles because of qualities like durability, water resistance, UV protection, and antimicrobial properties. Beyond that, they also offer specialised functions for specific domains such as flame retardancy, stain resistance, abrasion protection, and anti-static qualities. Such enhancements have made fabrics suitable for demanding applications across a wide range of sectors like from healthcare and security applications, to automotive, to sportswear and fashion. Finally, in addition to performance enhancement, coatings are also widely used to contribute to the aesthetic appeal of fabric by providing the possibility for distinctive textures, colours, and finishes.

Innovators in the field have already been demonstrating the ability to develop PFAS-free in specific domains, aligning with evolving regulations and the increasing demand for eco-friendly products (Chelsey Cook & National Geographic, 2024). Nevertheless, the substitution of PFAS coatings in textiles still remains a complex and largely unresolved issue, since there are many domains where substitution is a major challenge. Whereas there are emerging bio-based and hybrid coatings that offer certain levels of water and stain resistance in specific contexts, stakeholders have pointed at the issue that there are still quite some applications where substitutes fall short in terms of matching the allround durability and effectiveness. Also, alternative materials can struggle with issues like a reduction of wear resistance, lack of laundering durability, or decreased functionality under diverse conditions.

The BIO-SUSHY solution aims to contribute to solving these issues by developing an all round coating solution that is based on sol-gel technology. It offers an eco-friendly alternative by using water as a solvent and reducing harmful chemicals. It also focuses on using bio-based chemicals in the formulation. It has clear potential in terms of enhancing fabrics with durable, functional properties such as water- and oil repellency while maintaining flexibility for customisation. This makes sol-gel coatings a promising, sustainable, high-performance option for a wide range of textile applications.

Safety and sustainability priorities in the value chain

This section provides a summary of the relevant key challenges and priorities within the disposable paper food packaging value chain. The focus here is to describe the impacts of current practices and the way these challenges can help establish a way forward for the BIO-SUSHY SSbD approach to building its value chains.

PFAS exposure & environmental impact of coatings

In the current textile coatings value chain, non-polymeric PFAS such as fluorotelomers are prevalent, while polymeric PFAS dominate in other textile applications. PFAS are widely used in product categories like outdoor clothing, workwear, upholstery, and industrial textiles, each with unique requirements for performance, durability, and sustainability. In most textile value chains where PFAS

is strongly present, substitution and sustainability priorities are heavily based on health, safety and environmental issues. Fluorotelomers, prominent in PFAS-based textile coatings, are linked to a range of health impacts, including cancer, genetic mutations, reproductive harm, immune system toxicity, and damage to specific organs. In the textile case, an important concern is dermal exposure: PFAS substances, including those used in dyeing, finishing, or coatings such as flame retardant coatings, antimicrobial agents, and PFAS-based treatments, can transfer to the skin during prolonged contact. This issue is also relevant for clothing, upholstery, and other home textiles that frequently come into direct contact with humans. Oral exposure is another concern, particularly in children's products where mouthing behaviors increase the risk of chemical ingestion. Finally, abrasion during regular wear or use, further contributes to exposure by releasing microfibers and particles. This is evident in clothing and home textiles and extends to industrial and technical applications where textiles experience friction-intensive processes.

Moreover, both polymeric and non-polymeric PFAS can leach from textiles over time, particularly during washing, contributing to long-term pollution and human exposure. Abrasion also releases PFAS into the environment while washing amplifies these environmental concerns as textiles release PFAS and other microplastics and chemical residues into wastewater during every wash cycle. This problem is most pronounced in frequently washed textiles such as clothing, bed linens, and industrial uniforms. For technical and industrial textiles, harsher washing or cleaning conditions exacerbate the release. Degradation further adds to these issues, as textile coatings lose their structural integrity under physical stress, UV radiation, or harsh cleaning conditions. The slow degradation of technical and industrial textiles, which are often designed for durability, complicates these challenges further. Addressing these issues requires a balance between durability and environmental responsibility, prioritising sustainable materials while ensuring degradation processes do not worsen pollution.

Finally, the European Environmental Agency (EEA) highlights that rising textile consumption has significantly increased PFAS levels in waste streams, exacerbating pollution. In 2020, each European consumed an average of 14.8 kg of textiles, including 6.0 kg of clothing, 6.1 kg of household textiles, and 2.7 kg of shoes. Despite growing awareness of textile waste, more than half of discarded textiles still end up in landfills or are incinerated. PFAS-coated materials in these waste streams present unique challenges. Conventional recycling methods, such as mechanical recycling, are mostly incapable of separating coatings from fibers, resulting in the downcycling of textiles into lower-quality materials like insulation or industrial rags. This effect is even stronger in technical textiles, where multiple chemical treatments create significant barriers to efficient recycling. PFAS-coated textiles further exacerbate these challenges, as residual chemicals persist in recycled materials, limiting their safety and potential applications. In incineration, they release PFAS into the air, contributing to atmospheric pollution, while in landfills, PFAS coatings leach into soil and groundwater, where they accumulate, posing long-term environmental risks.

Figure 8: EEA overview of environmental and human exposure to PFAS from different phases of the lifecycle of textiles. Source: (Lofstedt, 2024)

The pervasiveness and complexity of PFAS applications in textiles

Apart from the increasing knowledge about the impact of PFAS use in textiles, an important issue is the sheer size of the PFAS issue in this value chain. According to the EEA, about one-third of all PFAS used in the EU go into the textile sector (including both coating and non-coating applications). This wide extent of applications poses significant challenges and priorities for substitution in the textile value chain. On the one hand, it reinforces the urgency of the sector's transition to safer, more sustainable alternatives. That is to say, if viable sustainable solutions are found for textiles, it would mean a big step for a more sustainable, PFAS-free future overall. On the other hand, the widespread application of PFAS in the sector in itself represents a major challenge in itself. As already indicated, PFAS are deeply entrenched in the textile industry due to their critical role in meeting diverse performance demands. Stakeholders expect that substituting PFAS in such a diverse range of applications is inherently complex, since alternatives must deliver equivalent functionality across varying conditions. It requires balancing a wide range of criteria regarding environmental safety, human health, and functional requirements.

Emerging solutions, such as bio-based and biodegradable coatings and innovative non-fluorinated chemistries, show promise in reducing PFAS dependence but they also face challenges in achieving comparable durability and resistance, especially for technical textiles exposed to extreme conditions. Finally, important to note here is that the textile sector has a history of regrettable substitutions, where replacements for hazardous chemicals have introduced new environmental or health concerns. Thus, developing alternatives that meet stringent performance demands without compromising sustainability or safety is a critical priority for the industry.

Need for traceability, closed-loop systems and more responsible consumption

Finally, the PFAS coating issue is part of the larger context of the difficult environmental and social footprint of textile value chains. The production of PFAS-based coatings relies on complex and energy-intensive chemical synthesis processes, requiring fluorinated raw materials such as fluoropolymers and perfluorinated intermediates. These chemicals are predominantly manufactured in large-scale hubs in China, the United States, and parts of Europe. This type of concentration of production, coupled with global export to textile-producing regions like China, India, and Southeast Asia, highlights the challenges of oversight and regulatory consistency across supply

chains. An important issue here is the fact that while the EU has stringent chemical regulations, imported textiles often lack equivalent scrutiny, leaving PFAS content largely unknown.

A shift toward more sustainable practices will require significant advances in recycling technologies. Developing systems that can deconstruct and purify coated textiles will be critical to enabling circularity. Similarly, policies such as extended producer responsibility (EPR) and the EU Waste Framework Directive (which mandates separate textile collection systems from January 2025) are driving increased attention to traceability and waste management. However, existing textile recycling systems across Europe face notable gaps in capacity, efficiency, and alignment with sustainability goals. For instance, while textile collection initiatives are expanding, much of the collected material is exported to countries in Africa and Asia, where inadequate waste management infrastructure often results in uncontrolled pollution, local dumping, or open burning.

In conclusion, achieving traceability and transparency is a key factor for the future of a sustainable textile value chain, from waste management to sourcing and production of coatings. In this context, SSbD principles can help these efforts by providing transparency in terms of environmental and health risks associated with chemical inputs. Beyond that, stakeholders point at the opportunities for improvement connected to the adoption of digital tools and material tracking systems such as the digital product pass (DPP). This can lead to enhanced traceability, ensuring that every stage of the value chain is aligned with sustainability objectives. Ultimately, the global supply chain complexity associated with PFAS underscores the need for responsible consumption. Beyond technical innovations, shifting consumption patterns toward fewer, longer-lasting, and more sustainably produced textiles will be critical. By integrating these priorities, projects like BIO-SUSHY can contribute meaningfully to reshaping the textile value chain while acknowledging the broader systemic challenges that remain.

Relevant priorities for BIO-SUSHY

- There is an urgent need for PFAS-free coatings to reduce the environmental & health impact of textile (& textile waste).
- Reducing both health and environmental effects requires innovations in material design, such as the development of fibers that shed less during washing, as well as safer chemical treatments that minimise harmful leaching.
- Prioritising the replacement of PFAS-based coatings with safer, high-performance alternatives, while improving the overall environmental footprint of coating processes, is essential for driving a sustainable transformation.
- Ideally, new coating solutions should increase recycling-compatibility which can further minimise environmental contamination during disposal.
- Addressing the recycling and end-of-life phase of textiles requires systemic change, including improved infrastructure for textile collection, sorting, and recycling across Europe.

- Developing closed-loop systems for sourcing and recycling coating materials as part of the SSbD approach in textiles, can help ensure that PFAS replacements deliver long-term environmental and health benefits. This is also related to the recycling & end-of-life stage
- There is an increase of policies focused on recycling and end-of-life solutions - such as EPR and DPP. These can help push the market towards sustainable solutions.

BIO-SUSHY innovation opportunities and value chain considerations

A major issue when it comes to textile coatings is that many (existing) substitutes, such as silicones or waxes, often fail to deliver similar performance levels to PFAS-based coatings and may alter the fabric's feel or appearance, thus not satisfying all the requirements (e.g. flame-retardancy), consequently limiting their applicability. The complex requirements for achieving desired functional characteristics, along with concerns about long-term efficacy and environmental impact of alternatives. For manufacturers seeking to transition away from PFAS-based solutions, this adds up to a complex set of challenges.

The BIO-SUSHY solution shows promise to face these challenges. Its aim is to further develop innovative coatings, based on the combination of sol gel chemistry, polyacid and epoxy functions and the addition of functional additives. These should provide a sustainable alternative to traditional PFAS-based treatments, preferably in a wide range of textile coating domains. The solution is based on a patent developed by two of the BIO-SUSHY project partners (Rescoll & IFTH, patent EP4086386). By combining durability and functional properties with environmentally friendly materials, this type of coating has the potential to minimise ecological impact while offering significant performance benefits.

To demonstrate its applicability, the coating is tested on three textiles (cotton, polyester, and a cotton/polyester blend) using a tablecloth and other home textiles as the base product. The focus is on the finishing composition for textiles, aiming to enhance various properties like wrinkle resistance, ease of ironing, and durability during washing. Furthermore, it increases flexibility of the textiles, as well as a soft touch. Beyond the PFAS issue, this composition does not release formaldehyde, which is often an issue with traditional textile coatings based on urea-formaldehyde. This adds to its possibility to become a more environmentally friendly option, thus representing a step towards safer, more sustainable textile coatings that offer improved functionality without the drawbacks associated with PFAS based coatings.

BIO-SUSHY solution:

Hybrid sol gel coating (RESCOLL/IFTH)	Formulation content: up to 30% biobased	Up to 25/75 inorganic/organic ratio	Solvent: Water	Application: Padding, fast curing; 3-5 min at 100-195°C
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- Coating solution is a water-based hybrid sol gel with a strong focus on using bio-based contents in its formulation.
- The solution has high organic content to enhance the coating's flexibility for textile

applications

- Initially, coatings are applied onto three textiles—cotton, polyester, and a cotton/polyester blend, but are planned to have wider applicability in later stages.
- Precursor-synthesised sol-gels along with functional chemicals will be deposited onto textile fabrics in one step by padding. This is a dipping procedure where excess formulation is squeezed out by the rollers from the textile fabrics. The method allows the liquid formulation to penetrate between the fibre in the fabric.
- Afterwards, this is cured in an oven or by UV processes.

Raw materials & sourcing

There are several challenges in the raw materials and sourcing stage, particularly with regards to balancing the technical performance requirements of the coating with the ecological and ethical considerations of sourcing materials. Issues such as resource scarcity, the environmental impact of chemical production, and the need for transparent supply chains make this a complex but essential step in driving sustainability. Careful attention must also be given to aligning material choices with broader industry trends, such as the move toward renewable feedstocks and circular economy principles. Below are the key considerations for the most important raw materials used in the BIO-SUSHY hybrid coating solution:

Epoxy silanes

Epoxy silanes play a critical role in enhancing the durability and functional performance of the BIO-SUSHY solution. They represent a cutting-edge approach to materials engineering, particularly in a context of multifunctional and sustainable solutions. Their novel combination of organic and inorganic properties makes them appealing in various emerging applications, albeit that currently, their reliance on petrochemical feedstocks presents sustainability challenges. Apart from carbon emissions, their chemical synthesis often involves hazardous intermediates, raising concerns about environmental and occupational safety. Addressing these issues is crucial to aligning the production and use of epoxy silanes with broader sustainability goals.

Here, it is useful to remark that bio-based alternatives represent a promising avenue, also for BIO-SUSHY, considering its target to increase biobased content. Researchers are actively exploring renewable feedstocks, such as lignocellulosic biomass or agricultural by-products, as potential raw materials for synthesising epoxy silanes. These innovations can help reduce carbon footprint and increase eco-friendliness of the solution. In that regard, transparent practices, particularly in the form of comprehensive LCA can enable downstream stakeholders to make informed choices and prioritise sustainability in product selection.

Ethyl silicate binders

Ethyl silicate binders are commonly used in coatings for their ability to form durable, heat-resistant films. Traditionally derived from petrochemical sources, the manufacturing process of ethyl silicates is energy-intensive and often involves volatile organic compounds (VOCs), which contribute to air

pollution and greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, the disposal of waste products from their synthesis poses environmental risks, particularly when not managed within a closed-loop system. Nevertheless, their pivotal role in sol-gel chemistry enables a range of environmental benefits.

Unlike traditional coatings that often rely on high-VOC organic solvents and petrochemicals, sol-gel coatings can be formulated as low-VOC, water-based, or even solvent-free systems. Also, they currently do not appear to be a regrettable substitution for PFAS, as it does not have the same persistence, bioaccumulative, or toxicological concerns. Finally, ethyl silicate binders can be combined with bio-based materials such as lignin, chitosan, or cellulose to create hybrid coatings that merge the benefits of both organic and inorganic chemistry. In conclusion, developing formulations with reduced VOC emissions and improved biodegradability will support compliance with evolving environmental regulations and consumer demand for safer, more sustainable materials

Polycarboxylic acids

Polycarboxylic acids, including citric acid, are widely used in applications such as coatings and adhesives. The environmental impact of polycarboxylic acids often depends on their production routes, which may involve energy-intensive processes or reliance on petrochemical precursors. For BIO-SUSHY, citric acid offers a promising pathway for improvement, particularly when derived from agricultural byproducts or waste streams. Utilising feedstocks such as corn stover, sugarcane bagasse, or fruit waste not only reduces the competition for arable land but also exemplifies the principles of waste valorisation and circular economy. For other polycarboxylic acids, identifying production pathways that prioritise renewable feedstocks is essential. Innovations such as the use of lignocellulosic biomass or synthetic biology approaches to engineer microbes for efficient acid production can provide pathways to lower the environmental impact.

In addition to sourcing considerations, addressing the energy demands and emissions associated with polycarboxylic acid production is vital. Advancements in green chemistry, such as catalysts that reduce energy consumption or methods that integrate renewable energy sources into production processes, can significantly lower the carbon footprint of these compounds. Furthermore, developing closed-loop systems to recover and reuse resources within manufacturing operations aligns with global goals for sustainable industrial practices. By focusing on bio-based sourcing, encouraging supplier innovation, and adopting greener production technologies, the coatings and adhesives industries can take a leading role in redefining sustainability for essential chemicals.

Silicon-based organic polymers

Finally, silicon-based polymers offer critical functional properties, such as hydrophobicity and flexibility. Their production often involves high energy use and emissions. Ensuring these polymers are free from persistent chemicals, such as PFAS, is still a hurdle. Collaborating with suppliers who employ renewable energy and prioritise closed-loop production systems can mitigate sustainability concerns. Furthermore, seeking alternatives that maintain performance while reducing reliance on fossil-derived feedstocks is a promising area for innovation. Transparency in the polymer's life

cycle, including end-of-life considerations, is also vital for evaluating its overall environmental impact.

Production & processing

The promise of new coatings is that it allows manufacturers to offer specialised fabrics that stand out in competitive markets. By incorporating high-performance coatings, textile producers can tailor their products to specific niches, offering distinct advantages over competitors.

Regulatory safety and environmental standards

Ensuring compliance with evolving safety and environmental regulations is critical in the development of PFAS-free textile coatings, as the EU (REACH) and other global regulatory bodies continue to impose restrictions due to PFAS compounds' persistence and potential health risks. The project's environmental safety testing, including biodegradability, toxicity, and end-of-life impact assessments, helps ensure that new coatings do not introduce unintended ecological harm or impact user health. For PFAS-free alternatives to be viable, they must align with both regulatory goals and consumer safety expectations. Rigorous quality assessments and adherence to standards such as Oeko-Tex, Zero Discharge of Hazardous Chemicals (ZDHC), or Ecolabel certifications can help substantiate claims of safety, sustainability, and functionality. These measures not only build market trust but also facilitate the broader adoption of PFAS-free coatings in textile production.

Quality control & compliance requirements

Quality control and compliance requirements for PFAS-free coatings vary significantly across different textile types. Some sectors, such as technical textiles, face stringent testing and regulatory scrutiny due to their critical applications in safety, military, or medical fields, where performance and safety stand central. These textiles often undergo rigorous testing for durability, toxicity, and environmental impact to ensure they meet both industry standards and public safety regulations. In contrast, other textile types, like fashion fabrics or home textiles, are often not subject to the same level of oversight, thus having more lenient quality control practices, especially at the early stages of product development. Nevertheless, in these domains, other market demands, like consumer demand for more sustainable products, can certainly help establish new markets. This underscores the challenge of developing PFAS-free alternatives that must meet diverse expectations across different sectors. Given the early TRL of the coatings in question, navigating these varying regulatory environments, testing standards, and consumer preference constitute important considerations in the potential scaling and market adoption of the BIO-SUSHY solution.

Substitution risks

The switch from conventional to more sustainable coating chemistries, especially those intended to replace PFAS-based finishes, introduces substitution risks. These risks stem from uncertainties in several areas, including hazard profiles, potential long-term health effects, and product performance under real-world conditions. In addition, brands may face reputational challenges if

less-proven alternatives fail to match the reliability of established products, reinforcing resistance to change among both suppliers and manufacturers.

To address this, the project's focus on SSbD principles can be a valuable investment in helping to alleviate resistance, since the SSbD approach helps validate new formulations early on, supports data sharing, and ensures transparency regarding chemical content and safety. By proactively integrating these measures during the R&D stage, future products can achieve both high performance and improved environmental and health outcomes, thus reducing the concerns associated with substituting traditional coatings. Towards the later stages of the project, further collaboration with suppliers, manufacturers, and end-users and involving them in the development and testing of new coatings can help alleviate this issue in the form of fostering trust and ensuring that performance meets market expectations.

Use & application

Sol-gel coatings for safety, sustainability and comfort

Sol-gel coatings have high potential for overcoming many of the challenges posed by the need for PFAS alternatives. They offer multifunctional performance enhancements, such as water repellency, UV protection, and antimicrobial properties, without relying on substances like PFAS or other persistent chemicals. Their hybrid organic-inorganic structure provides exceptional durability, reducing the need for frequent reapplications and lowering overall material consumption. The technology also allows for precise control over the chemical composition, paving the way for safer, custom-designed coatings that meet the demands of both technical textiles and sustainable production practices. As the sol-gel process continues to evolve, it holds significant potential to redefine the future of safe and environmentally friendly textile coatings.

To make the advantages of sol-gel coatings clear to consumers and users, communication should focus on their tangible benefits in everyday use. For example, highlighting how sol-gel coatings offer longer-lasting protection by reducing the need for frequent maintenance or replacement. This can also emphasise specific features, such as superior water repellency that keeps textiles dry in wet conditions or UV protection that extends the lifespan of outdoor fabrics. Transparency about the coatings' safety, such as being free from harmful PFAS chemicals, combined with certifications or eco-labels, can build trust and reinforce their appeal as a sustainable choice (see more on that below).

Consumer quality standards

Generally, in the textile domain, quality control is crucial to ensure both safety and functionality. The extent and focus of testing will vary widely based on the manufacturing location, product type, and target market's regulatory environment. As the BIO-SUSHY solution is still in a development stage, these expected variation will result in different need for monitoring mechanisms and alignment with consumer protection. Especially at the current moment, new alternatives must meet stringent regulatory standards while delivering comparable performance to traditional PFAS-based options. This stage involves extensive testing to assess a range of factors, such as skin toxicity,

environmental impact, and performance under different conditions. Additionally, the durability and effectiveness of the coatings, such as water or stain resistance, are evaluated to confirm they meet industry requirements for specific applications, whether in textiles, packaging, or glass.

Labelling

In the use and application phase of textile coatings, labelling has long been a powerful instrument for distinguishing and promoting more sustainable products. By highlighting coatings that avoid PFAS substances, labelling can increase consumer and industry awareness of safer alternatives, driving market demand for greener practices. At the same time, it is important to note that references such as “PFOS-free” or “PFOA-free” have demonstrated to be misleading, as they do not necessarily guarantee that a product is free from the entire PFAS group. Various sectors have recorded instances in which these types of claims were inaccurate or overly simplistic.

Thus, to ensure credibility in the use and application phase, such labelling should be approached with care. By aligning with clear standards and being aware of/collaborating with widely recognised labels, projects like BIO-SUSHY, with its strong focus on SSbD, can help ensure that sustainability claims rest on a verifiable foundation, thereby reinforcing consumer confidence. In turn, this can support the broader adoption of SSbD products and frameworks in the textile domain, ultimately driving innovation towards more environmentally responsible and health-conscious solutions.

Overconsumption

Especially with regards to the consumption stage, simply replacing PFAS with other chemicals does little to address the root problem of textile overconsumption (and resulting waste). Indirectly, a truly sustainable solution requires more profound changes, not just in materials but in our approach to textile production and use. This could involve embracing longer product life cycles, prioritising reparability, and reducing the emphasis on performance-enhancing treatments where possible. Whereas this largely lies outside of the current BIO-SUSHY capabilities, it is important to try to align the project with projects that aim for responsibility in these domains too. More on this will be addressed in the sLCA.

Recycling & end-of-life

Enhancing Recyclability through Safer Coatings

Recycling and end-of-life management of textiles pose significant hurdles, yet shifting to more sustainable coatings can substantially improve outcomes. By eliminating PFAS-based treatments that impede fibre recovery, these coatings produce higher-quality recycling outputs and minimise contamination in the waste stream. Relying on environmentally friendly materials and designed for broad applicability, this BIO-SUSHY solution helps preserve the integrity of recycled fibres while delivering competitive performance.

Circular Future

A successful transition from linear to circular textile models calls for close cooperation among policymakers, recyclers, manufacturers, and consumers. Improving sorting processes, raising consumer awareness, and upgrading recycling infrastructure all play a critical role in strengthening end-of-life strategies. The BIO-SUSHY coating technology supports this collaboration by reducing chemical risks, bolstering product safety, and offering robust data on environmental impact. Through its approach, the project can foster industry-wide transparency and standards that ultimately simplify both recycling and remanufacturing efforts.

Durability and end-of-life impact

Merely substituting one chemical for another does not address the core challenge of overconsumption and waste in the textile industry. A more holistic approach involves designing products for durability, reparability, and an appropriate level of functionality, ensuring performance requirements are met without unnecessary chemical loads. By uniting durability with environmentally responsible materials, the BIO-SUSHY solution aims to demonstrate that coatings can be both high-performing and low-impact. By refining formulation and application processes through ongoing research, the project can strengthen the case for responsibly produced textiles, proving that high-performance finishes and reduced environmental impact are not mutually exclusive. This blend of innovation and sustainability will hopefully contribute to reduce disposable fashion, instead contributing to practices rooted in longevity and responsible resource use.

Towards a sustainable, safe, and transparent value chain

The transition to a sustainable, safe, and transparent value chain for textile coatings requires addressing critical challenges, particularly the replacement of PFAS, improving traceability, and strengthening regulatory frameworks. Achieving a sustainable, safe, and transparent value chain for textile coatings will depend on coordinated efforts across industry, policy, and technology development. By phasing out PFAS where feasible, improving traceability systems, and reinforcing regulatory measures, the textile sector can overcome existing barriers and contribute meaningfully to a safer and more circular future. This transformation requires continued investment and collaboration to ensure that the innovations of today become the standard practices of tomorrow.

Combining technological advances with market, regulatory, and societal needs

A successful transition away from PFAS in textiles requires aligning technological innovation with market demands, regulatory frameworks, and societal expectations. While viable alternatives exist for most applications, proactive industry-wide adoption is essential to minimise environmental and health risks. Eliminating PFAS early in the supply chain not only reduces contamination risks but also facilitates safer recycling and circularity efforts. Strong regulatory frameworks play a crucial role in scaling bio-based coatings, both by phasing out PFAS and by creating incentives for sustainable alternatives.

For BIO-SUSHY, addressing societal needs means not only developing PFAS-free coatings but also actively engaging with stakeholders across the value chain. Transparency about material choices and safety testing is key to building trust among manufacturers, brands, and consumers.

Collaborating with certification bodies and eco-labels can help validate claims of safety and sustainability, making it easier for end-users to recognise and choose responsible alternatives. Additionally, the project can contribute to public awareness by sharing knowledge on the benefits and trade-offs of PFAS-free coatings, supporting informed decision-making at all levels. Thus, by integrating technological advances with regulatory alignment, market accessibility, and public engagement, the project can help drive the systemic changes needed for a safer and more sustainable textile industry.

Contributing to the foundations for circularity

Moving toward a model that balances functionality with sustainability will likely require coordinated efforts across the industry, from material innovation to consumer education and regulatory frameworks that discourage harmful chemicals and overproduction. Also, markets with stringent regulatory frameworks have already demonstrated the viability of safer alternatives. For instance, the EU's increased scrutiny on PFAS in textiles and the Nordic Council's recent recommendation for a regional PFAS ban underscore the feasibility and demand for non-toxic, sustainable solutions (Krause et al., 2024). In this regard, as the industry is likely to open up toward safer coatings, traceability is increasingly becoming a cornerstone for transparency and accountability. Advanced tracking systems have the potential to ensure that bio-based materials are properly integrated throughout the textile supply chain, providing stakeholders with clear data on material origins and sustainability credentials. This transparency not only builds trust but also facilitates compliance with regulatory standards, ensuring that bio-based alternatives gain widespread acceptance and adoption.

As BIO-SUSHY is progressing, awareness of these systems can help its solutions align with regulatory standards, ensuring consistency and accountability across the value chain. The project can work towards embedding its solutions within existing circularity initiatives, ensuring that bio-based coatings are compatible with large-scale recycling and reuse systems to further strengthen the market viability of PFAS-free alternatives.

Textile coatings

Safety & sustainability priorities in the value chain

Exposure & impact

- Health risks
- PFAS release (e.g. washing & abrasion)
- Poor recyclability & persistence

Pervasiveness & complexity of PFAS

- PFAS dominance in textile VC
- Complicated performance demands
- Regrettable substitution

Need for traceable & closed-loop systems

- Oversight global supply chains
- Recycling capacity
- Traceability & responsible consumption

BIO-SUSHY innovation opportunities and value chain considerations

Raw materials & sourcing

Epoxy-silanes
 - Add durability & performance
 - Increasingly bio-based

Ethyl silicate binders
 - Durability
 - Aim: low-VOC
 - Increasingly bio-based

Polycarboxylic acids
 - Green chem. potential
 - Bio-based sourcing

Silicon-based org. polymers
 - Need to mitigate sustainability concerns

Production & processing

Regulatory safety & environmental standards are key to adoption of coating solution, ensuring safety, sustainability, and market trust

Quality control and compliance vary across sectors. Require testing while balancing market demands and reg. challenges

Substitution risks related to safety, performance, and market acceptance, can be mitigated through holistic SSbD approach

Use & application

Sol-gel coatings offer great promise for **safer, more sustainable & comfortable** textiles

Quality standards expected to vary rather widely by market & application

Effective **labelling** with verifiable claims can support consumer trust and adoption

To tackle **over-consumption**, solution should align with broad systemic change

Recycling & end-of-life

PFAS-free coatings' role in a solution to enhance **textile recyclability**

Maintain focus on BIO-SUSHY's part in **circular future**

Aim to combine high performance **durability** with **low end-of-life impact**

Towards a sustainable, safe, and transparent value chain

A successful transition away from PFAS in textiles requires **aligning technological innovation with market demands, regulatory frameworks, and societal expectations**, ensuring proactive industry adoption, early supply chain interventions, and strong regulatory support for bio-based alternatives.

Advancing circularity in textiles requires coordinated efforts across the industry, and BIO-SUSHY can contribute by **aligning its PFAS-free coatings with traceability systems, regulatory standards, and large-scale recycling initiatives to support long-term sustainability.**

3.3. Cosmetic glass coatings

Introduction

The cosmetics packaging industry has seen rapid developments, especially in high-end markets. Crucially, growing consumer demand for more 'natural' solutions significantly influences ingredient selection of cosmetics themselves, but also forces brands to seek out packaging solutions that use more eco-friendly solutions. As part of that trend, innovative use of materials like bamboo, bioplastics, and glass have gained prominence. In addition, many companies are adopting practices such as minimal packaging and lightweight materials to cut down on waste.

Also, the rise of social media and e-commerce has made visual appeal even more crucial, as packaging now needs to stand out, not just on store shelves but also in online images and user-generated content. These shifts are pushing brands to adopt designs that resonate with new types of consumers and audiences, often prioritizing bold, unique, and photogenic elements with eco-friendly aesthetics. The result is an increase in simple, minimalistic designs that convey both luxury and environmental consciousness. In this context, glass is increasingly (re-)gaining attractiveness.

Recent years have seen considerable developments in glass coating research for specialist solutions. Sol-gel technology has been expanding rapidly, enabling the development of multifunctional coatings through innovative precursor solutions and efficient processing techniques in a range of specific applications. This has constituted a promising avenue for advancing new types of PFAS-free solutions in response to growing sustainability demands. In this context, BIO-SUSHY aims to develop a solution that is both hydrophobic and oleophobic with a high sliding effect, allowing the content of cosmetic glass packaging to allow smooth dispensing of cosmetic products, regardless of their viscosity.

Safety and sustainability priorities in the value chain

This section provides a summary of the relevant key challenges and priorities within the disposable paper food packaging value chain. The focus here is to describe the impacts of current practices and the way these challenges can help establish a way forward for the BIO-SUSHY SSbD approach to building its value chains.

Glass packaging coatings to improve specific use-cases

The cosmetic glass case is a bit different from the other BIO-SUSHY cases in the sense that its emphasis on the aspect of (PFAS) substitution is less straightforward. Coatings in glass packaging are not as common as in the other BIO-SUSHY case studies: glass is inert, meaning it does not chemically react with (most) substances it comes into contact with. This chemical stability is one of glass' key advantages, especially for packaging sensitive products like food, beverages, and pharmaceuticals. Moreover, unlike many other packaging base materials, glass naturally provides an effective barrier against moisture, oxygen, and contaminants. Additionally, it is less prone to scratching or wear, reducing the need for protective or aesthetic coatings

However, the priorities here can be directly connected to the need for replacing plastic packaging. Crucially, an advantage of plastic packaging is that it often allows the recovery of almost 100% of

the content. This is either because of the surface properties of the plastic (which is generally more hydrophobic than glass), or because its flexibility allows containers to be squeezed to recover the content. These advantages are lost when plastic is replaced by glass. To mitigate that, specific surfactants can be used as additives in the content to allow sliding or slipping on the surface and consequently allow better recovery of the material.

Currently, to achieve this sliding effect, most solutions are based on PFAS or on liquid-impregnating solutions that are often not compatible with cosmetic applications. Moreover, a relevant factor is the cosmetics industry's current campaign to eliminate a whole range of additives, including surfactants, from their formulations. Also here, adaptation to the container can be beneficial. Thus, applying a coating on the inner surface of the glass packaging is a technological approach that can answer this request, provided that the coating does not lead to release of undesired or toxic components into the content. As a result, there is a clear case for coatings in specific glass packaging applications, potentially even beyond the current BIO-SUSHY use case.

Maximising the return to glass as a attractive sustainable packaging material

Beyond the mentioned considerations, coatings can provide aesthetic enhancements to glass, such as matte, glossy or colored finishes, which are valuable for branding in industries like cosmetics, premium beverages, and luxury food products. They can also add functionality, such as anti-smudge properties for clear perfume bottles or improved grip for glass containers used in wet environments, like shampoos or condiments. Additionally, sustainable, PFAS-free coatings can align with consumer and regulatory demands for environmentally friendly packaging solutions, while supporting lightweighting efforts by adding protection to thinner glass.

These kinds of innovations can help leverage the potential of glass as a sustainable packaging material. PFAS-free coatings offer a pathway to meet regulatory and consumer expectations for safer, environmentally friendly materials. Coatings can play a supporting role in these processes, enhancing durability and increasing aesthetic appeal. By addressing these priorities, glass packaging can strengthen its position as a key sustainable solution across various industries while aligning with the broader goals of circularity and bioeconomy.

Adjusting to changing consumer awareness

Increasing consumer awareness of environmental sustainability and health risks has significantly boosted the demand for high-quality glass packaging, particularly in industries like cosmetics, beverages, and premium food products. While glass has a strong image of being inherently safe, non-toxic, and infinitely recyclable, consumers are increasingly focused on potential issues with their use of glass (e.g. worries about heavy metals, structural weaknesses, and contamination during manufacturing), as well as with potential issues in the recycling process. It is likely that these kinds of concerns will get more attention in the future, since consumers have increasing possibilities to gather information on a wide range of issues. This will likely drive a push for stricter quality standards and advanced solutions, from which the glass packaging market can benefit. However it also entails the need for a solid focus on glass and glass coatings' safety and durability, while addressing its environmental impact.

Relevant priorities for BIO-SUSHY

- Develop PFAS-free coatings to address consumer and regulatory demands for safer and more sustainable materials in packaging.
- Enhance aesthetic features of glass packaging with coatings that offer matte, glossy, or frosted finishes, supporting premium branding in industries like cosmetics.
- Provide functional benefits such as anti-smudge properties for clear containers and improved grip for products used in wet or high-use environments.
- Align with circular economy goals by ensuring coatings are compatible with recycling systems as well as improving conditions for reuse, thus contributing to the broader sustainability objectives of the glass packaging value chain.
- Drive innovation in niche applications by exploring adjusted coating solutions that address emerging market needs and enhance the versatility of glass packaging.

BIO-SUSHY innovation opportunities and value chain considerations

As described above, manufacturers currently navigate a landscape of evolving regulatory requirements and consumer expectations. In this context, finding more safe and sustainable solutions that are cost-effective is central to consolidating and improving market position. In response, BIO-SUSHY is exploring the possibilities of advanced internal coating solutions. As already explained, the project's glass coating is not meant to directly substitute specific PFAS-based coatings. Rather, it is part of a broader remedy to the issue of PFAS and other toxins by replacing plastic packaging by glass packaging. As such, the use case of the coating for glass containers can help the transition away from plastic packaging.

BIO-SUSHY coatings aim to combine metal oxides with long organic chains to create a coating solution that is both water- and oil-repellent, durable, and substantially less toxic than current PFAS-based coatings. Like in the case of textile, sol-gel technology is used to develop an eco-friendly solution and further reduce dependence on harmful chemicals while focusing on the use of bio-based chemicals in the formulation. The use of biobased materials and water-based solvents is expected to reduce the environmental impact of these coatings. The coatings will also be designed to work on different types of surfaces, making them versatile in terms of recycling and reuse. Like PFAS coatings, the new hybrid coatings will remain stable over time. Additionally, these coatings, which are similar to glass in their properties being mainly based on organosilane chemistry, will offer better reuse potential and enhanced mechanical and chemical stability, making them a promising and sustainable option for cosmetic packaging.

Crucially, it also provides important innovation potential in the form of the improved sliding of cosmetic products in glass packaging. Cosmetic glass is one of the applications where this can be of great advantage. First and foremost, coatings for cosmetic glass can help ensure that the entire cosmetic product inside the container can be used without sticking to the container. Cosmetic products can be either water- or oil-based, rendering it useful that coatings exhibit both hydrophobic and oleophobic properties. This helps ensure low sliding angles, which facilitate an

easy flow of the product from the container. An important part of the development process of the BIO-SUSHY solution focuses on ensuring the smooth dispensing of cosmetic products, regardless of their viscosity. Currently, to achieve this, most of the coating solutions are either PFAS-based on PFAS or, based on liquid-impregnating coatings not necessarily compatible with the cosmetic application.

A great advantage of this smooth dispensing is that it helps to alleviate product waste, addressing a critical issue in the cosmetic glass packaging sector. Traditional containers often result in up to 20% product retention, leading to inefficiencies and consumer dissatisfaction. Creating a coating with a low-friction, non-stick surface, can enable nearly complete product evacuation. The outcome is a direct reduction in material waste across the product life cycle, benefiting manufacturers, consumers, and the environment. Thus, compared to conventional solutions that often rely on PFAS or other synthetic agents, the BIO-SUSHY solution aims to offer a sustainable alternative without compromising performance.

BIO-SUSHY solution:				
Hybrid sol gel coating (MANO)	Formulation content up to 25% biobased	5-15% Organic content	Solvent: Mix Alcohol/Water	Application: Spray; Curing, low temp (30min - 45 °C) or fast (1 min - 150 °C) or UV (1 min)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hybrid hydrophobic/oleophobic sol gel coating solution, biobased precursor Sol gel coatings are applied internally, using a long spray nozzle and different angled heads. Different curing options are explored, one low temperature (30 minutes at 45 °C), one rapid heating (1 minute at 150 °C), and finally a one-minute UV process The curing type is adapted to specificities of industrial spraying and the time of curing will be optimised based on covering the inner part of the glass containers 				

Raw materials & sourcing

The aim is to integrate hydrophobic components derived from natural, biobased sources, such as modified fatty acids and cellulosic material, into the glass coatings. This approach seeks to enhance the durability of the coatings while minimising the risk of harmful substances leaching over time. Additionally, the use of structured particles, whether biobased like cellulose or synthetic, along with controlled curing processes, is being explored to improve oil repellency. Particles treated with fatty acids are also being incorporated to further boost these properties. BIO-SUSHY coating solutions incorporate a range of raw materials, including alkoxysilanes, silicate compounds, carboxylic acids, fatty acids, and silicone polymers. These materials represent diverse functionalities, sustainability considerations, and industrial applications, each contributing to the unique performance of the coating solution.

Alkoxysilanes

Alkoxysilanes are silicon-based compounds widely used in coatings for their ability to bond organic and inorganic materials. They serve as coupling agents, adhesion promoters, and water-repellent agents. Typically synthesised from silica or other silicon sources, alkoxysilanes offer compatibility with sustainable chemistries.

The production of alkoxysilanes involves chemical processes that can require significant energy and solvents, posing challenges for sustainability. Efforts to improve their environmental footprint include exploring bio-based precursors and greener synthesis methods. Advances in these areas are crucial to reducing emissions and making alkoxysilanes more sustainable for widespread applications in coatings.

Silica particles

Silica itself is inherently non-toxic and environmentally benign. However, the extraction and processing steps can consume significant energy, especially when refining silica for high-purity applications. Circularity efforts, such as utilising industrial silica waste streams, offer promising solutions to reduce resource consumption and emissions. Furthermore, the inherently safe nature of silicates supports their role in more sustainable coatings.

Carboxylic acids

Carboxylic acids, such as acetic acid, play an essential role in coatings as pH adjusters, reaction facilitators, or solubilising agents. While traditionally sourced from petrochemical processes, bio-based alternatives are becoming increasingly viable, using agricultural byproducts or microbial fermentation.

The sustainability of carboxylic acids depends on the production process. Bio-based production methods reduce reliance on fossil fuels and often have a lower carbon footprint. However, when sourced from crops, the environmental impact depends on agricultural practices, including land use and water consumption. Balancing these factors is key to ensuring that carboxylic acids remain a sustainable choice in modern coatings.

Fatty acids

Fatty acids, typically derived from plant oils such as palm, soy, or sunflower, are integral to biobased coatings. Their hydrophobic and biodegradable nature makes them attractive for eco-friendly formulations, where they function as surfactants, plasticisers, or lubricants.

The sustainability of fatty acids depends heavily on responsible agricultural practices. For instance, unsustainable palm oil production can lead to deforestation, biodiversity loss, and greenhouse gas emissions. However, certifications such as the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) promote sustainable practices, mitigating these risks. Increasingly, fatty acids derived from waste feedstocks, such as used cooking oils, are being explored to further enhance sustainability. Such approaches reduce pressure on land use while supporting circular economy principles.

Silicone polymers

Silicone polymers, or polysiloxanes, are known for their flexibility, thermal stability, and water resistance. In BIO-SUSHY, they are used in the form of polydimethylsiloxanes (PDMS). Their properties make them invaluable in coatings that require protection against moisture, UV radiation, and extreme temperatures. Derived from silica, a renewable resource, silicones have a relatively sustainable origin, but their chemical synthesis is energy-intensive.

The durability of silicone coatings reduces the need for frequent reapplication, which offsets some of the environmental costs associated with their production. However, silicones are not biodegradable, posing challenges for end-of-life management. Current research focuses on developing recyclable silicones or designing hybrid materials that combine the performance of silicones with improved environmental compatibility.

In the current phase, extensive research and development efforts are undertaken to optimise the formulation of the glass coating. Experiments focus on various combinations of raw materials, test different formulations, and assess the performance characteristics of the coatings through laboratory testing. The goal of the BIO-SUSHY project is to develop a hybrid coating that is based on sol gel chemistry with high content in inorganic material (SiO₂) allowing the coating to be very similar to the glass material.

Cellulose

Cellulose, derived from plant biomass, is a renewable and biodegradable material with increasing relevance in coatings due to its ability to enhance both functionality and sustainability. In BIO-SUSHY, cellulosic materials are explored as structured particles to improve oil repellency and as a biobased hydrophobic component to strengthen coating durability.

The environmental benefits of cellulose depend on its sourcing and processing. Sustainably harvested cellulose from certified forestry or agricultural residues offers a low-impact alternative to synthetic particles. However, energy-intensive processing methods or excessive chemical modifications can reduce its overall sustainability. Innovations in green functionalisation techniques are key to ensuring that cellulose remains a viable, eco-friendly option in next-generation coatings.

Production & processing

The BIO-SUSHY development process focuses on producing coatings that can be cured quickly or at low temperatures, and that use water-based or low-alcohol solvents. By aiming to reduce toxicity and environmental persistence, the project seeks to avoid the long-term health and ecological risks linked to traditional PFAS-based solutions. In doing so, BIO-SUSHY strives to provide robust performance while also reducing waste, encouraging reuse, and improving aesthetics in cosmetic packaging.

Balanced sustainability claims

Although glass is often viewed as more sustainable than plastic, thanks to its infinite recyclability and lack of petrochemical origins, its production can be energy-intensive, involving high-temperature furnaces and heavy machinery. This leads to significant emissions and a higher carbon footprint

during manufacturing and transport. Nevertheless, ongoing sector-wide developments in areas such as renewable energy use, improved furnace design, and increased utilisation of recycled cullet (30% in cosmetic glass containers) are helping to reduce the environmental burden. These advances support the continued viability of glass as a sustainable choice for cosmetic packaging, particularly when combined with coatings like BIO-SUSHY that further help reduce post-use cleaning needs.

Holistic view on advantages of glass

Ultimately, the sustainability of glass depends on refining production, streamlining logistics, and harnessing innovative coatings that support reuse and recycling. By integrating PFAS-free solutions such as the one from BIO-SUSHY (which facilitate easier cleaning and safeguard product quality), glass packaging can become a stronger contender in the drive towards circular systems. However, choosing the best material requires a holistic understanding of factors like energy consumption (including in transportation), carbon intensity, and recyclability. To reinforce its approach, the project could continue benchmarking its coatings against alternative solutions in other work packages (especially WP4), and work with stakeholders to fine-tune formulations and explore collaborative strategies that promote the advantages of glass. This measured perspective ensures BIO-SUSHY not only delivers exceptional coating performance but also helps reduce the overall impact of cosmetic glass packaging.

Use & application

Sliding effect

Important market developments in this domain are on the one hand the replacement of plastic packaging causing a comeback of glass packaging, in order to reduce plastic waste. A crucial function of PFAS-based coatings in this case is to ensure a sliding effect. To satisfy the requirements in terms of durable aesthetic aspect (cleanliness), reduction of waste and the restriction of the use of some chemicals in the cosmetic products (as tensio-actives), glass container manufacturers are looking for internal coating solutions. These would help perfect sliding of the product.

Consumer appeal

Pristine and clean surfaces are important in the cosmetics industry, where packaging plays a vital role in brand perception and consumer appeal. The BIO-SUSHY solution focuses on a sleek and uniform finish, free from smudges or residue that may occur with uncoated glass or inferior alternatives. By maintaining the visual integrity of the packaging throughout its use, this solution elevates the overall aesthetics, setting a higher standard compared to conventional coatings.

Recycling & end-of-life

Glass packaging generally has a more sustainable reputation than plastic because it can be recycled repeatedly with minimal loss of quality. Manufactured from naturally derived raw materials rather than petrochemicals, glass does not release harmful substances into its contents, which appeals to health-conscious consumers. These attributes reinforce glass as an environmentally friendly and safe packaging material, making it particularly suitable for sectors that emphasise both product integrity and brand reputation.

Recycling and reuse

Recent advances in recycling infrastructure, such as more effective sorting technologies and collection systems, have boosted glass recovery rates and helped prevent valuable material from ending up in landfill. As one of the few materials that can be recycled indefinitely without degrading, glass supports circular economy initiatives by reducing reliance on virgin resources and lowering the environmental impact of production. At the same time, industries including cosmetics, are exploring cleaning and reconditioning processes, often involving high-pressure or chemical-free methods at an industrial scale, to extend the life of glass containers. Similarly, reuse options are being considered at a private scale, using home-cleaning and reuse schemes. These kinds of developments towards reusability align with sustainability targets by reducing waste, lessening demand for single-use items and maintaining stringent hygiene and brand standards.

Advancing circularity

A key obstacle to widespread glass reuse has been the difficulty of removing residues from coated containers, which can hinder both recycling and cleaning processes. The BIO-SUSHY project's PFAS-free coating offers a practical solution, making it easier to clean containers and support long-term use of glass packaging. Unlike conventional coatings that may leave chemical residues or complicate reuse, this new formulation simplifies the removal of product remnants, helping transition sectors such as cosmetics towards refill and reuse systems. Growing consumer demand for sustainability, coupled with policies like EPR and deposit return schemes, further accelerates this shift, positioning glass packaging and the BIO-SUSHY coating as pivotal elements in more responsible and enduring packaging strategies.

Towards a sustainable, safe, and transparent value chain

Outreach on solution's sustainability and safety

Glass packaging is celebrated for its chemical stability, inertness, and recyclability, making it a preferred material in industries like cosmetics, pharmaceuticals and premium beverages. However, coatings remain essential in specific applications, particularly to meet both functional and aesthetic needs. BIO-SUSHY's focus on developing PFAS-free coatings aligns with growing regulatory and consumer demands for safer and more sustainable alternatives and should be explicitly profiled as such. These coatings aim to combine hydrophobic and oleophobic properties, enabling a high sliding effect that reduces product waste by ensuring efficient product evacuation. By minimising the need for harmful additives and emphasising biobased and water-based materials, BIO-SUSHY contributes to reducing the environmental footprint of glass packaging.

Becoming part of cosmetic innovation

The cosmetics industry demands packaging that is not only functional but also aligns with brand aesthetics and environmental values. BIO-SUSHY coatings provide sleek, uniform finishes that enhance visual appeal, ensuring that packaging maintains its pristine look throughout its lifecycle and allows 100% (or close to) recovery of the cosmetic content. Also, the project's PFAS-free coatings simplify the cleaning and recycling of glass containers, facilitating their integration into

refill and reuse systems. Such innovations can support the growing industry and policy emphasis on circular economy strategies, helping transition cosmetic packaging towards more sustainable and enduring solutions. Transparent communication about the safety and sustainability of these coatings, supported by robust certifications and lifecycle assessments, is critical to building consumer trust. By addressing concerns about chemical leaching, residue removal, and recyclability, the BIO-SUSHY solution ensures glass packaging meets the highest standards of functionality, safety, and consumer confidence.

Cosmetic glass coatings

Safety & sustainability priorities in the value chain

Improve specific uses of glass packaging

- Enable content recovery
- Aesthetic & functional benefits
- Transition plastic → glass

Maximising return to glass

- PFAS-free coatings for better use of glass
- Enhance glass attractiveness: durable & circular

Consumer awareness

- Provide safe, high-quality glass
- Increasing consumer insights into packaging

BIO-SUSHY innovation opportunities and value chain considerations

Raw materials & sourcing

Alkoxysilanes:

- Bio-based precursors
- Greener synthesis

Silica particles:

- Circularity promises (e.g. industrial waste)

Carboxylic acids:

- Potential low carbon, bio-based sourcing

Fatty acids:

- Sust. agriculture & waste feedstock

Silicone polymers:

- Hybrid formulations
- Focus: glass similarity

Cellulose:

- Explored to improve functionality & sustainability

Production & processing

A focus on establishing **balanced sustainability claims** can help to align BIO-SUSHY with innovations in renewable energy and recycled content to reducing the footprint of its solution.

Holistic view on advantages of glass emphasizes the need for optimized production, logistics, and PFAS-free coatings like BIO-SUSHY to enhance recyclability and circularity.

Use & application

Sliding effect represents a clear advantage for glass packaging to replace plastic while ensuring smooth product dispensing, cleanliness, and compliance with cosmetic industry requirements.

Consumer appeal in cosmetics relies on pristine packaging, and BIO-SUSHY enhances visual integrity with a sleek, smudge-free finish that outperforms conventional coatings.

Recycling & end-of-life

Recycling and reuse opportunities can benefit from improved sorting technologies and cleaning processes, enabling glass to support both industrial and private reuse initiatives.

Solution has clear potential in **advancing circularity** in cosmetic packaging, aligning with sustainability policies and consumer demand for refillable packaging.

Towards a sustainable, safe, and transparent value chain

BIO-SUSHY's solution should increase its understanding and outreach on how **sustainability and safety** in cosmetic glass packaging as a whole can be strengthened by its solution, as it improves product evacuation, minimises harmful additives, and supports environmental goals.

Pushing the solution as part of **cosmetic innovation** can improve BIO-SUSHY's profiling: its enhances both aesthetics and functionality, enabling sleek finishes, easier recycling, and alignment with circular economy strategies.

4. Perceptions, reservations & feedback stakeholder surveys

Surveys targeting key value chain stakeholders have helped to gain additional insights into stakeholder perspectives. Surveys were conducted by AXIA. They were launched on 22 October 2024 and closed on 22 November 2024 (1 month). Although one month passed, and the multichannel distribution strategy, the turnaround for survey respondents was low (Table 2).

Table 2: Number of responses for the different surveys.

Survey	Responses
Stakeholder Perception Survey	6
Consumer Acceptance Survey	12
Regulatory & Compliance Survey	2

Despite the modest sample size, these surveys provide valuable additional input that helps identify initial expectations, potential challenges, and opportunities for collaboration. AXIA will use these strategies to effectively communicate and resonate with the target audience, maximising the project's impact. As such, together with the insights developed from interview input, the findings serve as a further aid aligning the BIO-SUSHY's development with stakeholder priorities, ensuring that emerging solutions are not only technically viable but also relevant and responsive to real-world needs. In what follows, the results of the different surveys will be discussed.

4.1. Stakeholder Perception Survey

In the stakeholder perception, we observe a high level of industry readiness and a positive reception towards the new coatings. Respondents were coming from the coating, consulting, and textile and apparel sectors (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Stakeholder survey - Respondent's demographics.

Most respondents indicated familiarity with PFAS issues (4 out of 6) (Figure 10) and awareness of novel coating solutions (5 out of 6) (Figure 11). The positive attitude toward adopting new coatings (5

positive, 1 very positive) highlights the industry's readiness, suggesting a market eager for innovation (Figure 12).

Figure 10: Stakeholder survey - PFAS familiarity.

Figure 11: Stakeholder survey - Novel coatings awareness.

Figure 12: Stakeholder survey - Adoption attitude.

However, the survey also highlighted a tension between cost considerations and performance expectations. Technical performance emerged as the primary barrier to adoption (5 respondents), followed by concerns about cost (4 respondents) (Figure 13). In the support needed to help adoption, technical support and financial incentives received the highest votes (Figure 14).

Figure 13: Stakeholder survey - Barriers to adoption.

Figure 14: Stakeholder survey - Support needed for adoption.

Similarly, proven technical performance and clear cost benefits were again emphasised as the main measures needed to increase the adoption of the new coatings (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Stakeholder survey - Measures helping adoption.

Therefore, the stakeholder perception survey indicates a generally positive reception of the new coatings among stakeholders. Most respondents are familiar with PFAS issues and aware of efforts to develop alternatives. The main challenges appear to be cost and technical performance, suggesting that demonstrating cost-effectiveness and proven technical capabilities will be crucial for adoption (Figure 15).

4.2. Consumer Acceptance Survey

The consumer acceptance survey shows an educated and engaged consumer base. Consumer demographics and their PFAS awareness are depicted in Figure 16. The majority of respondents (6) were in the 35-44 age group, followed by 4 in the 25-34 group. They reported a high level of understanding about safe and sustainable products, indicating a knowledgeable target market.

Figure 16: Consumer survey - Awareness of PFAS chemicals across age groups.

Interestingly, this understanding seems to translate into a willingness to pay premium prices for safer products, with two-thirds of respondents indicating they would pay 6% or more for products with safe and sustainable coatings. This finding suggests a strong value perception that outweighs price sensitivity among consumers.

Figure 17: Consumer survey - Willingness to pay across age groups.

When asked to rank their concern in their decision-making, consumers choose health and safety, followed by product performance as top concerns, highlighting these two factors as two key selling points (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Consumer survey - Relative concerns in consumer decision-making.

Figure 19 shows the first-place breakdown by age group of the main concern driving consumer decision-making, evidencing how the 25-34 age group unanimously ranked health and safety as the most important factor in driving their decision.

Figure 19: Consumer survey - 1st place breakdown by age group for the relative concerns in consumer decision-making.

Studies backed up by science, clear labeling, and certification are the main trust mechanisms needed for consumers to choose novel bio-based products (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Consumer survey - Type of information needed across age groups to feel more comfortable about novel coatings.

The frequent mention of certification by trusted bodies and clear labeling as desired information sources emphasises the importance of third-party validation in building consumer trust. Similarly to Figure 20, also Figure 21 shows that consumers give special consideration to the ingredient list and whether the product is certified or labeled. This trend highlights the potential of certification and transparency (showing ingredient list) as the significant selling points for products utilising the new coatings.

Figure 21: Consumer survey - Relative importance of factors in consumer decision-making when evaluating safety.

Figure 22: Consumer survey – 1st place breakdown of the relative importance of factors in consumer decision-making when evaluating safety across age groups.

The 12 consumers who responded to the survey generally showed a good understanding and positive attitude toward safe and sustainable products. Also, there is a high level of awareness about PFAS chemicals and a willingness to pay more for safer alternatives. This suggests a favorable product market using the new coatings developed in the BIO-SUSHY project.

4.3. Regulatory and Compliance Stakeholder Survey

Despite its limited sample size (2 respondents) and their demographics not closely related to the identified target audience of regulatory bodies and public entities (respondents were one from consulting and one from research), the regulatory and compliance survey can still offer some preliminary insights into the regulatory landscape.

The perception of full or primarily complete alignment with EU regulations suggests a favorable regulatory environment for market entry. However, the survey identified some regulatory challenges, including REACH compliance, environmental impact assessments, and consumer safety concerns (Figure 23).

Figure 23: Regulatory & Compliance survey – Critical regulatory challenges identified by respondents.

In terms of support needed by industry stakeholders to meet regulatory standards, there was no clear consensus among the survey respondents, who indicated all the available options listed, i.e., financial support, closer collaboration with regulatory bodies, and more precise guidelines (Figure 24).

Figure 24: Regulatory & Compliance survey - Support needed by industry stakeholders to meet regulatory requirements.

On the other hand, both respondents emphasised the importance of collaboration between industry and regulatory bodies, indicating an opportunity for proactive engagement in shaping the regulatory framework for these new coatings (Figure 25).

Figure 25: Regulatory & Compliance survey - Role of regulatory bodies in facilitating adoption of new coatings.

While the sample size is very small, the responses suggest that the new coatings are well-aligned with current regulations. The emphasis on collaboration between industry and regulatory bodies indicates a potential pathway for addressing challenges and facilitating adoption. However, further research and relevant feedback is needed to validate these preliminary results.

5. Strategic priorities & next steps for BIO-SUSHY

BIO-SUSHY's solutions have clear potential to help reshape the coating landscape in a direction of more sustainable, safe solutions. Nevertheless, it is evident that the development of sustainable coatings necessitates a collective, multifaceted endeavour. Especially at this point in time, the successful reduction and elimination of the use of PFAS and replacement by alternatives needs R&D success in projects like BIO-SUSHY's, while it is simultaneously heavily contingent on external factors such as policy and regulation, broader industry innovation trends, and consumer readiness.

Having delineated the conditions of the BIO-SUSHY project and the associated challenges, needs, trends, and opportunities in its value chains, the insights need to be translated into strategic priorities for the project at its current stage. By uniting the divergent aims, motivations, and constraints into an actionable set of solutions, the project can aim to be a driver in the transition towards safer and more sustainable value chains.

In that regard, it is important to note once again that while the project is still largely taking place in laboratory settings, there is clear potential to move into more realistic or operational environments. Therefore, this section aims to help the project navigate the path towards PFAS-free value chains in different domains. In what follows, three clusters of priorities will be discussed, namely: BIO-SUSHY as a driver of safe and sustainable value chains; BIO-SUSHY as a platform for exploring novel

solutions to explore and implement stakeholder needs and consumer expectations; and finally BIO-SUSHY as collective that continuously (re-)aligns itself with circular & bioeconomy transformations.

For each of these priority clusters, explicit references will be made to other activities in the project. Furthermore, these ideas will be framed in the context of the future work that needs to be done BIO-SUSHY WP1, with regards to its focus on social acceptance and alignment.

5.1. Bolstering safe, sustainable and resilient value chains

To aid the further development and implementation of BIO-SUSHY's value chains according to SSbD standards, the project needs first and foremost to fulfill its basic task: developing high-quality coating solutions combined with rigid testing and standardisation procedures. In that process, several priorities can aid the project's long-term goals. In this cluster of priorities, recommendations are developed to cultivate further innovation, reinforce environmental stewardship, and strengthen the condition for (future) adoption of its coating solutions in terms of safety and sustainability. As discussed above, the imperative for sustainability is ever more pressing in the coatings industry, yet the path towards it is still highly uncertain. In this landscape, a concerted effort can help build a future where innovation aligns better with public health preservation and environmental stewardship.

Deepening value chain insights to foster SSbD

The focus on the key priorities in the BIO-SUSHY value chain provided useful insights into the relevant demands and preferences with regards to the project's solutions. Nevertheless, for the future there remains a critical need to address new decisions on (raw) materials and processes. Combining the right strategies for material sourcing and processing can significantly enhance project outcomes.

BIO-SUSHY itself offers unique resources that could advance future analyses of the project's value chains. For instance, the BIO-SUSHY Registry, primarily designed to collect eco-toxicological and physicochemical data, is becoming an increasingly well-structured dataset. Each material in the registry is identified through comprehensive metadata, including unique identifiers, chemical names, formulas, CAS numbers, batch numbers, and provider references. While this data currently supports the project's focus on safety and sustainability, it could also be repurposed to enhance value chain analyses as the project's solutions progress to a higher TRL. Recognising these additional applications of BIO-SUSHY tools, even beyond their original purpose, is vital for maximising their potential impact both within and beyond the project's lifetime.

Furthermore, integrating SSbD principles in coatings development presents significant opportunities to drive both innovation and environmental responsibility. SSbD encourages the proactive addressing of potential risks and environmental impacts. For coatings, this means prioritising non-toxic, renewable raw materials, reducing harmful emissions, and optimising the product life cycle to minimise waste and environmental footprint. Here, collaborating closely with (future) suppliers to source sustainable raw materials and setting clear sustainability criteria can ensure that eco-friendly practices are implemented at every stage of development. By enabling the identification and

resolution of potential challenges in material sourcing or process design before they affect the final product.

This way of embedding SSbD principles early can help to reduce regulatory hurdles and facilitate a smoother path to market implementation. Additionally, this proactive approach enhances adaptability to regulatory shifts and market demands, opening new market opportunities where green certification is increasingly required. Overall, integrating SSbD in both product development and early value chain stages allows the coatings industry to lead in responsible innovation, demonstrating a commitment to safety and sustainability while maintaining competitiveness in an eco-conscious market.

Finally, a focus on the life cycle of BIO-SUSHY solutions is essential for aligning with critical sustainability goals. Life cycle approaches like LCA, S-LCA and LCC emphasise the comprehensive evaluation of environmental, social, and economic impacts throughout a product's entire life cycle, from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal. This holistic approach enables companies to not only optimise their production processes but also reduce the broader societal and environmental footprints of their products. As already noted, WP4 has a strong focus on LCA, LCC and S-LCA. These will provide valuable insights into the resource use, emissions, and overall sustainability of products, facilitating more informed decisions that can drive long-term environmental, economic and social benefits. Also, they can help to mitigate risks from the outset by selecting safer, renewable, and less harmful materials.

Deepening value chain insights to foster SSbD: Concrete objectives and actions

Objective: Expand BIO-SUSHY's value chain insights to optimise material sourcing and process design under SSbD principles.

Action (1): Utilise the BIO-SUSHY resources that are meant to analyse material safety and sustainability from **WP3** to assess partnerships with suppliers committed to non-toxic, renewable materials, while proactively addressing regulatory requirements

Action (2): Integrate advanced **WP4** life cycle sustainability assessment tools (LCA, LCC and S-LCA) to guide the decisions throughout product development in order to reduce environmental, economic, and social impacts, and improving the market readiness of coatings through early sustainability validation.

Integration to resilient value chains

Attention to the further integration of BIO-SUSHY's bio-based coatings into resilient value chains can enhance the stability and sustainability of the project's future solutions while simultaneously advancing sustainability objectives. As already argued in the above, this can be done by carefully

choosing solutions that focus on sustainable raw materials. The **LCA**, **LCC**, and **sLCA (WP4)** already play a central role in assisting and monitoring this process. Here, fostering connections between bioeconomy initiatives and other efforts towards resilience can amplify the project's impact by positioning it among a range of sustainable and bio-based solutions that align with broader initiatives towards resilience and adaptation, supporting both sustainable material development and ecosystem restoration. Such synergies not only promote the circularity of bio-based solutions but also have a clear potential to reinforce the adaptive capacity of natural and human systems.

This approach exemplifies how resilient value chains can be more than robust and sustainable: They can actively contribute to addressing global challenges like climate change by bridging interdisciplinary gaps and ensuring mutual reinforcement across initiatives. Simultaneously, the concept of resilient value chains underscores the need to fortify supply chains against disruptions and vulnerabilities, in a world increasingly marked by significant unrest and insecurity. Whether stemming from geopolitical tensions, natural disasters, or other unforeseen contingencies, projects like BIO-SUSHY must take the possibility of unpredictable shocks and stressors into considerations. This is not only of relevance for the stability of the project's value chains, but it also plays a role since it presents an opportunity to align the project with real-world needs. For instance, lignin-based bio-coatings efforts can be connected to reforestation efforts to source sustainable raw materials or test solutions in environments affected by climate change.

Not only can these types of connections strengthen the R&D basis of the solutions being developed but it also ensures they are designed with systemic challenges in mind, increasing their potential for market adoption and societal impact. Finally, such collaborations can attract additional funding or stakeholder interest, as they demonstrate a commitment to addressing interconnected environmental and societal challenges.

Integration to resilient value chains: Concrete objectives and actions

Objective: Strengthen the integration of BIO-SUSHY's bio-based coatings into resilient value chains that help address environmental challenges and increase resilience to supply chain vulnerabilities.

Action: Build up awareness and potentially create partnership with bioeconomy initiatives to source sustainable raw materials, address both ecological and socio-economic challenges, and ultimately help establish networks that focus on circularity and resilience.

Harnessing global dynamics in sustainable innovation

To successfully scale sustainable coating innovations from their current early-stage development, it can be of use to exploit global dynamics, since these provide critical momentum and strategic guidance for market integration. Sustainability-focused value chains have increasingly become a competitive arena, with global markets driving innovation and investment, as companies and countries alike try to achieve leadership in environmentally responsible technologies and practices. Several markets closely connected to sustainability efforts, have already come to reflect global power dynamics (e.g. photovoltaics, battery technology, green hydrogen). In these markets, China and other countries in (Southeast) Asia increasingly dominate production and supply chains.

The EU is trying to strengthen its position by focusing on innovation, subsidies/industrial policies, and reducing its reliance on imports to bolster geopolitical leverage. The domain of bio-based, sustainable materials is expected to see similar dynamics. Currently, the EU aims to leverage its regulatory frameworks and R&D strengths to drive innovation in areas like high-performance bio-polymers and circular design. This competition is further intensified by the strategic need to reduce dependency on (petrochemical-based) plastics, alignment with ESG goals, and capturing market share in high-value applications. In this way, bio-based materials are emerging as a crucial arena for competition, branching out in different directions such as sustainable agriculture, eco-friendly manufacturing, renewable energy, and innovative construction materials.

At first sight, BIO-SUSHY is quite far removed from these kinds of dynamics. Nevertheless, in the years ahead, the project and its partners may find opportunities in a wide range of bio-based materials sectors but will simultaneously have to manage the shifts and developments in bio-based materials at the global level. Europe has a clear potential for maintaining its global position in the chemical industry by investing in the development of sustainable raw materials. It is exactly for this reason that one of the top priorities of the European Chemical Industry Council (Cefic) in its manifesto 'Teaming up for a Climate-Neutral and Competitive Europe' is a push towards material self sufficiency (Cefic, 2023). Especially when BIO-SUSHY's solutions manage to scale up successfully in more advanced TRL stages, these kinds of macro-developments are likely to become increasingly relevant, especially since they can help to strengthen the ecosystems within which the project's solutions thrive. **WP5's work on assessing market opportunities and developing new business plans** for innovative coatings serve as a great foundation for navigating these global dynamics and aligning with emerging trends in bio-based materials. Additionally, synergies and clustering activities from the same WP can foster strategic collaborations that enhance BIO-SUSHY's positioning in the competitive landscape.

Harnessing global dynamics in sustainable innovation: Concrete objectives and actions

Objective: Position BIO-SUSHY within the competitive landscape of sustainable materials to leverage global market trends and EU R&I policy.

Action: Foster awareness of global developments in bio-based materials, identify potential strategic collaborations within the EU's R&I ecosystem, and develop scaling strategies to align BIO-SUSHY's solutions with high-demand applications in emerging markets.

5.2. Aligning with stakeholder needs & consumer expectations

In an era where transparency and sustainability are at the forefront of societal and market expectations, aligning with stakeholder needs and consumer priorities is increasingly integrated into R&D processes. For BIO-SUSHY, at its current stage of development, this means actively seeking input and engagement from stakeholders to ensure the project's development trajectory resonates with evolving demands for safe, sustainable, and transparent practices. Doing so, the project can lay a strong foundation for future adoption and trust. This process involves not only understanding and addressing concerns but also demonstrating a commitment to proactive engagement, fostering credibility, and preparing for the regulatory and market landscapes that will shape the project's success.

Raising awareness of coating benefits

Beyond their environmental and health benefits, bio-based chemicals and coatings have great potential for superior performance characteristics, such as enhanced durability, improved resistance to corrosion, and greater versatility in application. In such a context, investing in bio-based technologies can be a great way of fostering responsible innovation and entrepreneurship, driving the development of tailored solutions for evolving market needs. However, widespread adoption remains hindered by a lack of awareness and understanding among the general public and businesses. Misconceptions and lack of knowledge about cost, effectiveness, and availability further complicate adoption. Addressing these barriers requires targeted education and outreach efforts to inform stakeholders at all levels about the benefits of bio-based products.

Effective communication is essential for raising awareness. Media campaigns, educational programs, and outreach events can highlight the environmental, economic, and societal benefits of sustainable coatings. Also here, WP5's work already demonstrates a promising outlook for the second half of the project. In combination with this work, WP1 can further try to foster contact and collaboration with government stakeholders, industry stakeholders, and research institutions to support the development and commercialisation of the project's solutions, aiming to ensure successful integration into mainstream markets. Finally, transparency efforts elaborated above can also help collaborative efforts across the value chain, enabling informed decisions and unified approaches to sustainability. Examples here can come from almost all WPs in terms of regular reporting on metrics like carbon footprint reductions and waste minimisation potential, thus establishing credibility, and encouraging collective action toward greener solutions.

Raising awareness of coating benefits: Concrete objectives and actions

Objective: Enhance public and industry understanding of the environmental, economic, and performance advantages of sustainable coatings, while fostering collaboration across the value chain.

Action: Use the project's targeted dissemination and communication strategies by integrating outreach efforts with stakeholder engagement initiatives to connect with government, industry, and research institutions. Leverage transparency efforts across all WPs, such as regular reporting on sustainability metrics, to establish credibility and encourage adoption of bio-based solutions

Promoting transparent standards and reliable certification schemes

BIO-SUSHY has prioritised safety and impact assessments early in the product development process. The project entails considerable investments in the development of advanced computational tools that enable the rapid evaluation of bioactivity and toxicological risks. By prioritising safer compounds and formulations at the initial stages, BIO-SUSHY aims to mitigate issues like regrettable substitutions, align with regulatory expectations, and reduce downstream costs associated with redesign or safety non-compliance. These proactive methods accelerate innovation while ensuring safety and sustainability remain central to the project's value chain.

From a social acceptance perspective, these activities represent great potential with regard to addressing growing public and regulatory concerns about the environmental and health impacts of chemical products. Transparency, early-stage safety assessments, and robust certification schemes are investments in a more open value chain. Open communication about chemical compositions, potential hazards, and lifecycle impacts is increasingly critical for building trust among consumers, regulators, and industry stakeholders. The activities in WP5, which focus on mapping the standardisation landscape and contributing to the development of future standards, play a crucial role in advancing these transparency and trust-building efforts.

Market credibility also hinges on transparent and reliable certification systems. Adhering to established schemes, such as the EU Ecolabel or Cradle to Cradle, demonstrates environmental performance and appeals to buyers who prioritise certified solutions. Additionally, WP5's focus on standardisation provides BIO-SUSHY with a strategic opportunity to shape emerging certification frameworks for bio-based coatings, including criteria for biodegradability, carbon footprint reduction, and non-toxicity. This dual focus—complying with existing certifications while influencing future frameworks—facilitates market access and positions BIO-SUSHY as a leader in sustainable, transparent practices.

Promoting transparent standards and reliable certification schemes: Concrete objectives and actions

Objective: Strengthen BIO-SUSHY's position as a leader in sustainable coatings by promoting transparency, engaging with certification bodies, and contributing to the development of reliable standards.

Action: Build on WP5's efforts in standardisation and transparency to align BIO-SUSHY's solutions with existing certification schemes and shape emerging standards for bio-based coatings. Foster collaboration with policymakers and certification bodies to ensure that criteria for biodegradability, carbon footprint reduction, and non-toxicity align with the needs of sustainable coatings

Consumer engagement in the development process

Engaging consumers in the development process is a key strategy for enhancing transparency and trust. Involving consumer groups and end-users in discussions about product formulations, safety measures, and environmental impacts ensures responsiveness to consumer needs and values. Methods such as surveys, focus groups, and participatory design processes can provide valuable feedback that shapes product features and enhances market alignment. The upcoming activities in WP1 will integrate

In a market where consumers are increasingly aware of product health and environmental implications, transparency about development decisions is crucial. Clear communication regarding ingredient choices, performance standards, and environmental trade-offs helps consumers understand and support the product life cycle. Such engagement demystifies the complexities of coatings development and invites stakeholders to participate in the journey toward safer, eco-friendly solutions.

BIO-SUSHY's value chains should aim to build these forms of engagement, fostering stronger relationships with consumers and stakeholders alike. By emphasising collaboration and transparency, the project can enhance its impact and readiness for broader adoption.

Support Dissemination and Exploitation Strategies

Finally, based on the survey findings, a set of integrated strategic actions to support the dissemination and exploitation of the BIO-SUSHY project results is proposed. The actions, along with the examples and the metrics to be used, are listed in Table 3. By applying these actions, the BIO-SUSHY project's end results, such as the bio-based linkers, the bio-based sol-gel, and organic thermoplastic powder coatings, as well as the safe bio-based food trays, are anticipated to be positively received by the market and increase their adoption rate.

Table 3: Strategic actions for project dissemination and exploitation based on surveys' results.

Action Name	Description	Tools Used (Examples)	Success Metrics
Targeted Cost-Benefit Messaging	Develop and disseminate precise, sector-specific cost-benefit analyses demonstrating the long-term economic advantages of adopting our BIO-SUSHY new coatings.	Social media posts; Website news; Brief videos; Case studies for the textile industry showing long-term savings; Webinars for food packaging sector	Number of downloads/views of materials; Increase in inquiries from target sectors
Technical Performance Showcase	Organise industry-specific demonstrations and trials to provide tangible proof of the coatings' technical capabilities regarding water and oil repellency compared to commercially available benchmarks.	Product demonstration videos; Live demonstration at industry fairs and trades	Number of attendees/participants; Percentage of positive feedback; Number of follow-up requests
Collaborative Innovation Platform	Create a platform for ongoing collaboration between the project team, sister projects, and industry stakeholders to refine coatings based on feedback	Online collaboration tools (e.g., Slack, Microsoft Teams); Idea management software; Online forum for coating formulators; Roundtable with industry partners	Number of active users; Quantity and quality of improvement suggestions; Number of implemented innovations

Educational Marketing Campaign	Launch a targeted campaign highlighting the benefits of BIO-SUSHY coatings.	Social media posts on eco-friendly food packaging; Influencer partnership for sustainable fashion	Reach and engagement rates; Increase in brand awareness; Growth in consumer inquiries
Certification Preparation	Prepare documentation and processes for future certifications	Pre-audit of certification requirements; Compilation of necessary test results	Percentage of certification requirements addressed; Readiness score from certification experts
Regulatory Roadmap	Develop and share a detailed regulatory roadmap outlining how BIO-SUSHY coatings meet or exceed current regulations	Interactive timeline of EU chemical regulations; Compliance checklist for different industries	Number of stakeholders accessing the roadmap; Reduction in compliance-related queries; Positive feedback from regulatory bodies
Collaborative Research Initiative	Establish a joint research program with regulatory bodies to address challenges and influence future frameworks	Joint study with ECHA on long-term environmental impact	Number of joint publications; Influence on policy discussions
Industry-Regulatory Forum	Organise regular forums bringing together industry stakeholders and regulatory representatives	Quarterly virtual roundtable on bio-based coatings and emerging technologies	Attendance rates; Diversity of participants; Number of actionable outcomes/agreements

5.3. Leveraging circular & bioeconomy transformations

Across various sectors, transformative shifts from using traditional, mostly non-renewable, environmentally harmful materials, towards more sustainable, eco-friendly alternatives. Whereas skepticism and doubts persist regarding the depth and authenticity of this transition, its influence on value chain transformation is undeniable. Also in the coatings and chemicals sector, the

alignment with these sustainability trends has evolved from being a choice to becoming a strategic necessity. For BIO-SUSHY, being deeply embedded in this shift, existing initiatives, frameworks, and innovations can be useful and inspirational. This necessity of synchronising with established trends, entails a focus on the significant advancements and best practices that have emerged within the realm of sustainable coatings. By recognising and building upon existing trends, BIO-SUSHY can enhance its own value chains and accelerate the transition to a more sustainable future.

Positioning as pioneers in R&I ecosystems

The development of bio-based coatings is closely tied to the broader transformation toward sustainable chemistry, a key driver of the EU's transition to a green and circular economy. This transition offers significant opportunities for innovation and collaboration, particularly for research-driven initiatives like BIO-SUSHY. By actively engaging within established R&I ecosystems, the project is well-positioned to collaborate with innovation clusters working on related technologies. These connections can enable access to joint funding opportunities, shared infrastructure, and pathways for faster market adoption of sustainable solutions.

In this context, the project's focus on early-stage research and technology development (TRLs 3 to 6) places it at the heart of innovation ecosystems, providing a platform to lead in the development of transformative solutions. By leveraging this position, BIO-SUSHY can amplify its impact through partnerships that accelerate progress toward industrial-scale implementation while contributing to the broader circular bioeconomy. Ongoing advancements in renewable bio-resources and sustainable technologies present a pivotal moment for the coatings sector. Thus, the focus should be on fostering an innovative environment where EU industries can lead the transition to sustainable and resilient supply chains. By maintaining its pioneering role in research and actively engaging with stakeholders, BIO-SUSHY is uniquely positioned to contribute to this transformative shift.

Positioning as pioneers in R&I ecosystems: Concrete objectives and actions

Objective: Establish BIO-SUSHY as a recognised leader in R&I ecosystems for bio-based coatings.

Action: Proactively build strategic partnerships with innovation clusters and R&D programs, to leverage shared infrastructures and funding opportunities, thus helping to accelerate the development and adoption of sustainable coating technologies.

Aligning with civil society initiatives

Civil society initiatives are increasingly central to driving the adoption of sustainable practices, providing a vital bridge between scientific innovation and societal engagement. This is also very much the case in each of the BIO-SUSHY value chains. Think of organisations like the Food Packaging Forum which provides insights on chemicals in packaging and its health impacts, to

Fashion Revolution that advocates for transparency and fair practices in fashion, to Close the Glass Loop which is a European partnership focusing on material stewardship in glass packaging, collection and recycling. Many more examples can be provided here. The analysis for this deliverable, especially in the interviews, has already aimed to demonstrate awareness of NGO's, community groups, and environmental advocacy networks. Nevertheless, it has only grasped the insights present at such organisations. Continuing this work in further stages of the project can help incorporate diverse perspectives into the development and implementation of BIO-SUSHY solutions. Further alignment with these efforts can amplify the project's impact by ensuring that bio-based coatings address not only satisfy industrial needs but also broader societal demands for environmental and social responsibility.

Such alignment would also provide a platform for pilot studies, feedback mechanisms, and increased public visibility. By engaging civil society, BIO-SUSHY can aim to help in the process of fostering public trust and create a shared sense of ownership over sustainable innovations. This can hopefully also help address societal barriers to adoption, such as scepticism toward bio-based materials or lack of awareness about their benefits. Co-creating initiatives, such as workshops or campaigns on sustainability in materials and coatings, can ensure that the project's solutions are framed in ways that resonate with diverse audiences, from environmentally conscious consumers to industry stakeholders. Moreover, aligning with grassroots movements and community-driven efforts could open opportunities for funding, advocacy, and policy support, positioning BIO-SUSHY as a key contributor to the broader bioeconomy and its societal transformation.

Aligning with civil society initiatives: Concrete objectives and actions

Objective: Strengthen BIO-SUSHY's societal impact by aligning with civil society initiatives to foster public trust and broader acceptance of bio-based coatings.

Action: Be aware of NGOs, community groups, and environmental advocacy networks that highlight the environmental and social benefits of bio-based coatings. Ensure that these efforts focus on demonstrating how BIO-SUSHY solutions contribute to societal goals like waste reduction, plastic use minimisation, and promoting circularity in materials.

Strengthening synergies with industry

Fostering partnerships with other research projects and industrial stakeholders working on bio-based and sustainable coatings is essential for advancing the project's goals. By sharing knowledge, lessons learned, and identifying potential synergies, these collaborations can accelerate technology development while avoiding duplicative efforts. The project is uniquely positioned to benefit from cross-disciplinary research initiatives and innovation hubs experimenting with sustainable alternatives, as these provide fertile ground for collaboration.

Aligning with broader trends in the circular and bioeconomy opens significant opportunities for the project, particularly as the global shift toward sustainability accelerates. Initiatives led by industry

leaders, NGOs, and academic stakeholders increasingly advocate for safer, more sustainable materials, including PFAS-free alternatives. These efforts range from corporate strategies for industry transformation to grassroots campaigns calling for systemic change. By engaging with these diverse actors, the project can play a pivotal role in translating research into real-world applications and innovative solutions.

In its initial phase, the project focused on internal development, building the technology, and fostering interdisciplinary collaborations on key topics like SSbD, materials and coatings R&D, and QSAR modeling. These efforts have positioned the project as a thought leader in its domain. However, the next phase offers an exciting opportunity to increase external engagement. Active participation in ongoing industry discussions, alignment with policy dialogues, and showcasing the project's solutions will enhance its visibility, relevance, and impact.

The value chain analysis has already highlighted areas where the project's solutions can increase impact, providing insights into the needs and considerations of key stakeholder groups. Expanding outreach to industry players, innovation clusters, and policy networks will help align the project with market demands and societal expectations. This strategic engagement can also create new opportunities for collaboration, driving innovation and ensuring the successful integration of the project's solutions into circular and bioeconomy landscapes.

To fully realise this potential, the project must focus on strengthening existing industrial partnerships while expanding its partner base. Collaborations with pioneering organisations and industry leaders can harness collective knowledge and resources, ensuring that sustainable practices are impactful, scalable, and market-ready. This alignment will not only meet regulatory and consumer expectations but also create a collaborative ecosystem that fuels innovation and positions the project at the forefront of sustainable coating technologies.

Strengthening synergies with industry: Concrete objectives and actions

Objective: Expand BIO-SUSHY's industrial partnerships to drive innovation and facilitate the integration of bio-based coatings into real-world applications.

Action: Proactively engage with industry leaders, cross-disciplinary initiatives, and innovation hubs to build partnerships that align with market demands and the circular bioeconomy.

6. Closing remarks

For a prosperous future, the urgency for sustainability transitions across economic systems and societies has become undeniable. Innovative solutions are central to the viability of this process, as they demonstrate the feasibility of large-scale transitions to more sustainable alternatives. In the realm of materials and coatings, the establishment of value chains and infrastructure necessary for a net-zero, sustainable, and circular economy remains a significant challenge. Nevertheless, safety and sustainability are becoming increasingly important, not only from a regulatory and consumer standpoint but also as drivers of technological progress in a competitive landscape. To maintain their position and stay competitive, industries must innovate continuously and align with evolving market demands. In that regard, the next generation of coatings represent a unique opportunity for EU industries to leverage their strong R&D capabilities.

As BIO-SUSHY's solutions advance toward higher TRLs, it is essential to prioritise the development of responsible and sustainable value chains. Though still in their formative stages, early attention to sustainability can lay robust foundations for future growth. This includes prioritising renewable and biobased materials, ensuring that supply chains are transparent, ethically sourced, and environmentally responsible, and finally working to optimise future manufacturing processes for energy efficiency and waste minimisation. Sensible alignment of these efforts with broader industry trends will be vital. Moreover, collaboration and communication with stakeholders across the value chain are indispensable to maximise resource efficiency and minimise environmental impact. By embedding sustainability into every stage of the process, BIO-SUSHY can not only meet current regulatory and consumer demands but also contribute to a more sustainable future for the respective industries (food packaging, textile, glass packaging).

To enhance the success of the bio-based coatings value chain, social acceptance efforts in WP1 will aim to position BIO-SUSHY's work among stakeholders from industry, civil society, academia, and policymakers, fostering the transition to circular, bio-based solutions based on SSbD principles. Collaborative coalitions will be crucial to further establish supportive policies, securing financing, and building the infrastructure necessary to scale up bio-based alternatives while ensuring both environmental and economic sustainability.

The advancement of sustainable coating technologies not only supports the circular economy but also sets a powerful example of how innovation, collaboration, and environmental stewardship can intersect. These efforts have the potential to act as a catalyst for broader transformation. By integrating targeted research, pilot implementations, and strategic partnerships, BIO-SUSHY showcases a pathway for industries to move beyond incremental changes and embrace a sustainable future. In doing so, it also helps demonstrate how solutions to global challenges can emerge through a commitment to laying the groundwork for a thriving, sustainable Europe.

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8. Annexes

Annex I – Stakeholder Perception Survey Responses

Table Annex 1: Stakeholder perception survey responses (1 of 2).

Id	Start time	Completion time	What sector does your organization operate in?	How familiar are you with the issues around PFAS in your field?	Are you aware of the efforts to develop novel hybrid and biobased coatings?	How do you perceive the importance of using sustainable coatings in your field?
1	22/10/2024 10:43	22/10/2024 10:45	Consulting	Very familiar	Yes	Somewhat important
2	22/10/2024 11:56	22/10/2024 12:03	Consulting	Not familiar	No	Somewhat important
3	22/10/2024 16:50	22/10/2024 16:52	Coating	Very familiar	Yes	Somewhat important
4	23/10/2024 12:13	23/10/2024 12:17	Textile & Apparel	Very familiar	Yes	Very important
5	25/10/2024 11:34	25/10/2024 11:35	Coating	Very familiar	Yes	Very important

6 07/11/2024 11:22 07/11/2024 11:23 Coating Somewhat familiar Yes Very important

Table Annex 2: Stakeholder perception survey responses (2 of 2).

Id	What are your initial thoughts on adopting these new coatings in your products?	Do you have any reservations or concerns about using these new coatings? (If Yes, please specify in the 'Other' box)	What would be the biggest barrier to adopting these coatings in your products?	What support would you need to adopt these coatings?	What would make it more likely for you to adopt these new coatings?
1	Positive	No	Technical performance;	Financial incentives;	Compliance with regulations;Proven technical performance;Clear cost benefits ;
2	Positive	No	Technical performance;	Technical support ;	Clear cost benefits ;Proven technical performance;
3	Positive	No	Cost ;Technical performance;	Financial incentives;Technical support ;	Proven technical performance;Sustainability & Safety;Clear cost benefits ;
4	Very positive	No	Cost ;Technical performance;Regulatory compliance;	Technical support ;Regulatory guidance;Financial incentives;	Positive consumer feedback;Compliance with regulations;Proven technical

performance;Sustainability
& Safety;

5	Positive	No	Cost ;	Regulatory guidance;	Compliance with regulations;Proven technical performance;Sustainability & Safety;
6	Positive	product variability	Cost ;Technical performance;	Technical support ;Regulatory guidance;	Proven technical performance;Sustainability & Safety;Clear cost benefits

Annex II – Consumer Acceptance Survey Responses

Table Annex 3: Consumer acceptance survey responses (1 of 2).

Id	Start time	Completion time	What is your age group?	How well do you understand the benefits of safe & sustainable products?	Are you aware of PFAS chemicals in consumer products?	What factors do you consider most important when evaluating a product's safety? (rank in order of importance)
1	22/10/2024 10:26	22/10/2024 10:29	25-34	Well	Yes	Certification or labels (e.g., organic, non-toxic);Ingredient list;Brand reputation;Reviews and testimonial;
2	22/10/2024 10:32	22/10/2024 10:35	35-44	Very well	Yes	Ingredient list;Certification or labels (e.g., organic, non-toxic);Brand reputation;Reviews and testimonial;
3	22/10/2024 10:47	22/10/2024 10:55	25-34	Very well	Maybe	Ingredient list;Certification or labels (e.g., organic, non-toxic);Brand reputation;Reviews and testimonial;
4	22/10/2024 10:45	22/10/2024 11:00	35-44	Well	Yes	Ingredient list;Certification or labels (e.g., organic, non-toxic);Reviews and testimonial;Brand reputation;
5	22/10/2024 11:45	22/10/2024 11:52	35-44	Very well	Maybe	Ingredient list;Certification or labels (e.g., organic, non-toxic);Reviews and testimonial;Brand reputation;
6	22/10/2024 12:03	22/10/2024 12:04	18-24	Well	No	Certification or labels (e.g., organic, non-toxic);Reviews and testimonial;Ingredient list;Brand reputation;

7	22/10/2024 12:42	22/10/2024 12:46	35-44	Very well	Yes	Ingredient list;Certification or labels (e.g., organic, non-toxic);Brand reputation;Reviews and testimonial;
8	23/10/2024 10:38	23/10/2024 10:41	25-34	Somewhat	Maybe	Certification or labels (e.g., organic, non-toxic);Ingredient list;Brand reputation;Reviews and testimonial;
9	23/10/2024 10:46	23/10/2024 10:48	25-34	Well	Maybe	Ingredient list;Certification or labels (e.g., organic, non-toxic);Brand reputation;Reviews and testimonial;
10	24/10/2024 12:46	24/10/2024 12:48	45-54	Very well	Yes	Ingredient list;Certification or labels (e.g., organic, non-toxic);Brand reputation;Reviews and testimonial;
11	25/10/2024 11:35	25/10/2024 11:37	35-44	Very well	Yes	Ingredient list;Reviews and testimonial;Certification or labels (e.g., organic, non-toxic);Brand reputation;
12	08/11/2024 01:24	08/11/2024 01:25	35-44	Very well	Yes	Certification or labels (e.g., organic, non-toxic);Ingredient list;Reviews and testimonial;Brand reputation;

Table Annex 4: Consumer acceptance survey responses (2 of 2).

Id	How important is sustainability to you when choosing products?	How likely are you to purchase products with safe & sustainable coatings (e.g., on textiles, food trays, cosmetic containers)?	Please rank in order of importance your concerns you may have about products with new coatings.	How much more would you be willing to pay for products with safe & sustainable coatings?	What type of information would help you feel more comfortable with these products?
1	Somewhat important	Very likely	Health and safety;Environmental impact;Product performance;Cost;	6-10% more	Certification by a trusted body;Consumer reviews;
2	Very important	Likely	Health and safety;Environmental impact;Cost;Product performance;	6-10% more	Scientific studies ;Clear labeling on products;
3	Very important	Very likely	Health and safety;Environmental impact;Product performance;Cost;	More than 10%	Certification by a trusted body;
4	Very important	Likely	Product performance;Cost;Health and safety;Environmental impact;	6-10% more	Clear labeling on products;
5	Very important	Likely	Product performance;Cost;Environmental impact;Health and safety;	More than 10%	Scientific studies ;Consumer reviews;Certification by a trusted body;Clear labeling on products;
6	Somewhat important	Neutral	Product performance;Cost;Health	Up to 5% more	Clear labeling on products;Consumer reviews;Scientific studies

and safety;Environmental impact;

7	Somewhat important	Very likely	Health and safety;Product performance;Environmental impact;Cost;	6-10% more	Clear labeling on products;Certification by a trusted body;
8	Somewhat important	Likely	Health and safety;Cost;Product performance;Environmental impact;	Up to 5% more	Clear labeling on products;Certification by a trusted body;
9	Somewhat important	Neutral	Health and safety;Cost;Product performance;Environmental impact;	Up to 5% more	Consumer reviews;Clear labeling on products;Scientific studies ;
10	Very important	Very likely	Health and safety;Environmental impact;Product performance;Cost;	More than 10%	Scientific studies ;Certification by a trusted body;
11	Somewhat important	Likely	Cost;Product performance;Health and safety;Environmental impact;	More than 10%	Scientific studies ;Consumer reviews;Clear labeling on products;Certification by a trusted body;
12	Somewhat important	Likely	Cost;Product performance;Health and safety;Environmental impact;	0% (I would not pay more)	Certification by a trusted body;Clear labeling on products;Scientific studies ;

Annex III – Regulatory & Compliance Stakeholder Survey Responses

Table Annex 5: Regulatory & Compliance stakeholder survey responses.

Id	Start time	Completion time	What sector does your organization operate in?	How aligned do you believe the new coatings are with current EU regulations on chemicals and food safety?	What are the most critical regulatory challenges for these new coatings?	How important are new types of safe and sustainable coatings in achieving regulatory aims?	What support do you think industry stakeholders need to meet regulatory requirements?
1	22/10/2024 11:00	22/10/2024 11:02	Consulting	Mostly aligned	Compliance with REACH regulations ;Consumer safety concerns;Environmental impact assessments;	Somewhat important	Closer collaboration with regulatory bodies;Financial support;
2	25/10/2024 11:37	25/10/2024 11:39	Research	Fully aligned	Compliance with REACH regulations ;Food safety standards;Environmental impact assessments;Consumer safety concerns;	Somewhat important	Clearer guidelines

Annex IV – Survey Distribution Insights

 BIO-SUSHY Project ...
663 followers
Tmo

Help Shape the Future of Sustainable Coatings

🗨️ We're seeking input from stakeholders, consumers, and regulatory bodies to shape the future of sustainable coatings. Your insights will help us develop innovative and eco-friendly solutions.

It will take only 2 minutes to share your perspective and be part of the change! 🌱

🏢 Stakeholder - Coating formulators, food service companies, textile producers, cosmetic producers, and interest groups [<https://lnkd.in/dxJGSh2j>]

👤 Consumer - Potential users of products with the new coatings [<https://lnkd.in/dXFADdT2>]

🏛️ Regulatory & Compliance - Regulatory agencies and public entities [<https://lnkd.in/dTuWPMaa>]

#BIOSUSHY #PFASFree #consumers #coatings

European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA)

Materia Nova / Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, DAIMON / AXIA Innovation GmbH / AcumenIST / Ecozema srl società benefit / IFTH / ITENE / ProtoQSAR / Applus+ , Applus+ Rescoll / Seven Past Nine / SIKEMIA / UNE - Asociación Española de Normalización / University of Leeds / Wood K plus - Kompetenzzentrum Holz GmbH / Centre for Social Innovation

ZeroF project / PROPLANET Project / Tornado Project

BIO-SUSHY - Surveys for Stakeholder, Consumer, Regulatory - 4 pages

BIO-SUSHY

Help us shape the future of coatings

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Stakeholder

Help us identify potential concerns and barriers in novel coatings adoption.

Take 2-3 min to fill out the form: <https://forms.office.com/6c70d6c4260a>

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Consumer

Help us develop products that meet the needs and desires of consumers like you.

Take 2-3 min to fill out the form: <https://forms.office.com/6c70d6c4260a>

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Regulatory & Compliance

Help us assess potential regulatory hurdles and compliance requirements.

Take 1-2 min to fill out the form: <https://forms.office.com/6c70d6c4260a>

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